

D4.1 Implementation of R17: Non ICT Innovative Social Actions

WP 4 Creation of Innovative Social Actions

BCNecologia

Public Report M12

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1	Introduction	1
2	General description of the Social Action Program	2
2.1	Objectives.....	2
2.2	Methodology.....	3
2.3	Main characteristics of the Social Action Plan	5
3	Definition of Target Groups for the Social Actions	7
4	Key messages	11
5	Description of the ICT based tools	14
6	Environmental Education Program in Zamudio	16
6.1	Participation of the local groups on the project definition and monitoring (Z1) ↗	17
6.2	Schools Campaign and activities (Z2) ↗	18
6.3	Food waste prevention campaign (Z3) ↗	21
6.4	Commercial Activities Campaign (Z4) ↗	24
6.5	Composting (Z5) ↗	26
6.6	PAYT- New collection scheme with monitoring use of containers system (Z6) ↗	28
6.7	Zero waste ecosystem (Z7) ↗	31
6.8	Zero waste events (Z8) ↗	33
6.9	Miscellaneous (Z9) ↗	35
7	Environmental Education Program in Halandri.....	39
7.1	Educational Centers activities (H1) ↗	40
7.2	Actions at Technical University (H2) ↗	42
7.3	Food separate collection and treatment (H3) ↗	44
7.4	Commercial Activities Campaign (H4) ↗	46
7.5	Collection of nappies (H5) ↗	48
8	Environmental Education Program in Seveso	51
8.1	Citizens' sensitization. An innovative "Funny door to door sensitization on residual waste" (SE1) ↗	52
8.2	Zero waste events and campaigns "Virtuous Households" (SE2) ↗	55
8.3	Ecoevents (SE3) ↗	58
8.4	Pay as you throw introduction-communication (SE4) ↗	62
8.5	Promotion campaign of reusable nappies (SE5) ↗	65
8.6	Reusable nappies campaign for nursery school (SE6) ↗	68
9	Environmental Education Program in Cascais.....	71
9.1	ID/PAYT containers system (C1) ↗	72
9.2	Tourist engagement (C2) ↗	75
9.3	Waste 4 Think Schools (C3) ↗	77
10	Other Integrative Social Actions.....	82
10.1	Other Integrative Social Actions.....	82
11	Expected results	84
12	Follow up methodology	85
12.1	Quantitative reporting	85
12.2	Qualitative reporting.....	86
12.3	Specific monitoring for Zamudio's action	88

12.4	Documental updating.....	103
13	Interaction with Communication & Dissemination Plan and Business Model.....	104
14	Annexes	107
14.1	Calendar	107
14.2	Common indicators	108
14.3	Baseline survey proposal.....	109
14.4	Final Survey Proposal, example.....	112
14.5	ANNEX Details of the integration of the W4T ICT tools in the SA.....	114
14.6	ANNEX analysis of Zamudio surveys	132

Figures:

Fig. 1	Questionnaire for social actions definition	3
Fig. 2	New dashboard to upload social actions, pictures and KPI's associated.....	4
Fig. 3	Social Action Plan scheme.....	5
Fig. 4	Habits change scheme.....	6
Fig. 5	Target groups tackled in the Social Action Plan by pilot.....	11
Fig. 6	FORECAST: Zamudio's social actions forecast.....	38
Fig. 7	FORECAST: Halandri Social Actions calendar	50
Fig. 8	FORECAST: Seveso Social Actions Calendar	70
Fig. 9	FORECAST: Cascais Social Action Calendar	81
Fig. 10	Social Actions Monitoring	85
Fig. 11	Factsheet of the qualitative reporting	87
Fig. 12	The concept of social footprint (SF)	89
Fig. 13	The reusable packaging materials distributed in the Zamudio campaign: reusable containers for meat and fish, bitsybags for fruit and vegetables, Bocn'Roll, Isothermal bag.....	90
Fig. 14	Life cycle diagram for the 'BAU' scenario.	92
Fig. 15	Life cycle diagram for the 'Campaign' scenario.	93
Fig. 16	Interaction among WP4, WP6, WP7 and WP9.....	106
Fig. 17	Social Actions forecast	107
Fig. 18	Excel: QUESTIONNAIRE OF BUYING HABITS (answers) BASELINE.....	132
Fig. 19	QUESTIONNAIRE OF BUYING HABITS (replies) BASELINE	132
Fig. 20	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1.....	133
Fig. 21	Excel: QUESTIONNAIRE OF BUYING HABITS (answers) BASELINE.....	134
Fig. 22	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1.....	135
Fig. 23	Excel: CUESTIONARIO DE LOS HÁBITOS DE COMPRA (respuestas) BASELINE	135
Fig. 24	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 4.....	136
Fig. 25	Table of consumption per capita and rations.	137
Fig. 26	Table of rations and annual package. Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1	138
Fig. 27	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1.....	138
Fig. 28	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2.....	139
Fig. 29	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2.....	139
Fig. 30	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2.....	140
Fig. 31	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2.....	140

Fig. 32	Table of rations and annual package. Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2	141
Fig. 33	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2.....	141
Fig. 34	Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 3.....	142

1 Glossary of abbreviations and acronyms

CA	Citizen App
DP	Digital Project
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EC	European Commission
FA	Food App
ICT / IT	Information and Communication Technologies
MG	Mobile Game
Mx	Number of Month
PAYT	Pay As You Throw
STEAM	Educational approach to learning that uses Science, Technology, Engineering, the Arts and Mathematics
SA	Social Action
W2S	Waste 2 Sort game
W4T	WASTE4THINK Moving towards Life Cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems
WP	Work Package

2 Introduction

This deliverable describes the environmental education strategies to be followed during the implementation of each pilot, including the most innovative social actions to reach a high level of awareness and change in habits from the different targets involved.

One of the objectives of Waste4Think is to develop best environmental education and awareness strategies and to present it along with the implementation of all the required actions to undertake the demonstrative objectives of the Pilots sites. The final goal is to reach a high rate of empowerment and awareness and finally, a change in consumption and waste management habits among the different stakeholders involved in the implementation of the different actions.

Due to the importance of the environmental awareness for a real change of behaviors and habits, a full description of objectives, methodologies and monitoring of the different actions is a must in the framework of the waste4think project. So that, the deliverable includes a full program that defines a strategic and integral awareness/participation campaign for each pilot, new innovative social actions are defined to promote prevention and social empowerment. General strategy and each communication are deeply described and scheduled, application methodology deployed, ready to be implemented in each pilot. Monitoring and quantification methodology of the results are especially highlighted in each Social Action Program.

As it is the aim of this report to have a deep description of the environmental education actions in terms of systemic and comprehensive pilots strategy on social actions, it also includes the integration of the use of the IT tools developed during the project. A further description of the use of the IT tools (learning materials, apps, serious games, etc.) will be described in the Deliverable 4.2 (M28).

This Deliverable includes the complete Social Action Program decided in each Pilot and defined in the questionnaires about social actions fulfilled during the months M3-M10, taking into account that there is a continuous follow up and updating of the actions.

First updating was been done in M24 to introduce the new developments in the environmental Educational Program in each pilot.

New update has been done in M30 integrating D4.2 with the forecast of the ICT tools based solutions use.

The entire document has been updated taking into account the latest monitoring changes, as well as links to the website where all actions implemented are recorded and described.

3 General description of the Social Action Program

3.1 Objectives

The general objective is to promote a change of thinking and behavior in people towards the society of sustainability. Social Actions are necessary for a real and smoother achievement of this change of habits.

All the Social Actions foreseen in the W4T project has the same background: involve the different target groups defined to develop critical thinking, adopt the values of the culture of sustainability and act in accordance with them. The social actions are a strategy of environmental education and not only environmental communication.

The objectives and guiding principles for developing environmental education are as follows:

Participation - to provide individuals, groups and societies with opportunities to be actively involved in exercising their skills of environmental citizenship and be actively involved at all levels in working towards sustainable development.

Knowledge - to help individuals, groups and societies gain a variety of experiences in, and a basic understanding of, the knowledge and action competencies required for sustainable development

Values - to help individuals, groups and societies acquire feelings of concern for issues of sustainability as well as a set of values upon which they can make judgments about appropriate ways of acting individually and with others to promote sustainable development

Skills - to help individuals, groups and societies acquire the action competence or skills of environmental citizenship - in order to be able to identify and anticipate environmental problems and work with others to resolve, minimize and prevent them

Awareness - to create an overall understanding of the impacts and effects of behaviors and lifestyles - on both the local and global environments, and on the short-term and long-term.

To achieve the objectives, the pilots have developed a global strategy to integrate all society in the process of environmental education and to influence the whole population, without excluding any sector.

To ensure the effectiveness and integration of all the actions a monitoring system has been defined for each strategy and communication/sensitization activity (from collection of real data to social activities as forums, focal groups, social network scraping, etc.). The objective is to obtain quantitative and qualitative data to evaluate the success of each strategy and improve the education strategies in order to reach the maximum number of results and number of participants, and maximize the cost-effectiveness of the sensitization strategies.

A periodical critical review of the social, economical and environmental KPIs are going to be done, in order to evaluate the progress and achievement of the results. The actual results will be checked against the predicted values.

If significant deviations are recorded, a rigorous revision of the particular task will be made to detect possible problems and possible solutions.

3.2 Methodology

The deliverable includes the social action plan foreseen at the current moment (M12), usually a combination of strategic and integral awareness/participation campaigns and specific and dedicated activities for each pilot.

To define these activities a questionnaire was developed, sent to all pilots leaders to be fulfilled and discussed with them in order to achieve a good description and forecast of all the actions, assuring the coherence with the objectives, the monitoring methodology and the integration of the IT tools when needed.

Fig. 1 Questionnaire for social actions definition

A most integrated and dynamic way to upload the information generated was developed. The called “Data Model” is a platform and a repository to the social actions. Using the Url <https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/> the pilots and interested citizens are allowed to have access to every action.

Fig. 2 *New dashboard to upload social actions, pictures and KPI's associated.*

Example of questionnaire

At this moment, 21 actions have been defined and described. For each activity the next information has been requested:

- Name of the communication action
- Description
- Objectives
- Promoter
- Executer
- Key messages
- Target group description
- Tools and means needed to implement the action
 - Human resources.
 - Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents
 - Educators and informers. Tasks and contents

- Other
 - Equipment
 - Communication materials
 - IT tools developed in the framework of the W4T project
 - Other IT Tools
 - Other materials (leaflets, posters, etc.)
 - Calendar of the action
 - Monitoring strategy and expected results
 - Expected feedback of the results to the target group or general audience
 - Best practices identified related to the action

The deliverable has been developed with this information and later updating. A final version with the results of the monitoring and updated information of the actions finally developed will be done at the end of the project, with special attention to the results of the IT tools implementation and use.

3.3 Main characteristics of the Social Action Plan

Fig. 3 Social Action Plan scheme

The Social Action Plan is divided in “**Strategies**” (described in this deliverable) and “**Actions**”. Foreseen development of the Strategies is described in this document and the Actions will be deeper described in the monitoring reports with the real results of their application in each pilot. Starting from the definition of the target groups involved, the key messages and the partial objectives/waste fractions to work in, as well as the results of the questionnaires described in the previous section, the Environmental Education Strategy has been developed.

The Waste 4 Think Social Actions Plan is innovative in many senses:

1. The actions are aimed to achieve an active interaction with the target groups involved, through participation groups, citizens science actions, demonstrative activities;
2. Also, a mid-term planning has been done for each strategy line and synergies among them, integrating the Ecosolutions that are being developed during the project, especially the “educational ones” but also the PAYT system or others;
3. But one of the most specific innovation that we are working on is in the monitoring of these social actions, both in qualitative and quantitative way, to assure not only the replicability but that lessons learnt are recorded and could be used to be more efficient and effective in the future

To achieve these objectives and for recording purposes Social Actions have been split in **Social Actions type** and **Social Actions implementation** (see chapter 13.2).

To define the social actions, a change of habits “flow line” has been taken into consideration. From information to awareness, and from awareness to an effective change of habits, there are some barriers that we must overcome. Actions to be taken are something more than just “informative”, aspects as participation on decision making, creation of a positive climate and “social belonging” feelings, exemplarity of public bodies, economic incentives, among others are the kind of activities being developed during waste 4 think.

Fig. 4 Habits change scheme

4 Definition of Target Groups for the Social Actions

Different target groups have been detected and described. The same categories have been used for other purposes assuring the integrity and consistency of the different documents generated in the frame of the waste4think project:

Citizens

Citizen is a person who is entitled to enjoy all the political, civil and social rights and privileges granted by a state to the people comprising its constituency, and are obligated to obey its laws and to fulfill his or duties as called upon.

A citizen is characterized by age and gender. From a social point of view, in order to finalize sensitization and awareness actions, a citizen could be also characterized by his/her level of awareness with regard to a specific argument and his/her membership in a social group.

Students

Student is a person who learns, usually someone who attends an educational institution. The Student could be enrolled or attends classes at a school, college or university. We usually refer to formal education.

SME

Small and medium enterprises whose personnel numbers fall below certain limits. Small enterprises have up to 50 employees, and medium-sized enterprises have up to 250 employees.

The category of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) is made up of enterprises which employ fewer than 250 persons and which have an annual turnover not exceeding 50 million euro, and/or an annual balance sheet total not exceeding 43 million euro.

Researchers

Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products processes, methods, and systems, and in the management of the projects concerned.

Associations

Group of people who have joined together for a particular purpose, ranging from social to business, and usually meant to be a continuing organization. It can be formal, with rules and/or by-laws, membership requirements and other trappings of an organization, or it can be a collection of people without structure. An association is not a legally-established corporation or a partnership.

Educational centres

Refers to the physical space where people gather or congregate for education, receives, assimilates and learned knowledge and to acquire, in addition, cultural and behavioural sensitization by previous generations. It is usually differentiated by age groups in compulsory education or by specific thematic.

Domestic generator

Domestic generators are citizens that in their households generate waste as a result of the ordinary day-to-day use that would end up in the municipal bins.

Tourist

A tourist is a person who moves from his usual environment to another geographical point, being absent from his usual place of residence for more than 24 hours and spending the night in the other geographical point.

The pilot area Cascais is located near one of the most popular beaches in Lisbon region and, as it has a striving tourism economy, there is a strong demand on accommodation. As the target area is residential, mostly apartments, it is common to have a short-term renting offer dedicated to tourists usually coming during summer time.

Additionally, some smaller apartments are also rented to immigrants and other rotating demand. Usually in older buildings more orientated top second house service.

Despite having a similar waste production as other residents (domestic) they are in a completely different group of users as they are unable to get the information on waste production and, most of the times, they do not pay the water bill where waste cost is explained.

There is a need to develop a specific communication campaign to both landlords and tourists to ensure the understanding of the project's goals and bin access.

Commercial generators

Commercials generators are all those groups such as hotels and restaurants, markets, offices, stores, theatres that in their business generate waste (solid and non-hazardous) that would end up in the municipal bins.

Industrial generators

Industrial generators are all those groups that in their industries generate waste (may be solid, liquid or gases held in containers- are divided into hazardous and non-hazardous) that would end up in the municipal bins or in specific bins.

Food waste generators (Cooked food waste generators and expired food waste generators)

Cooked food waste generators may be restaurants, caterings... that sell prepared food and have in a weekly or monthly basis expired product that would end up in the municipal bins. Expired food generators may be Supermarkets or local shops that sell food products (vegetables etc) and have in a weekly or monthly basis expired product that would end up in the municipal bins.

Nappies generators (Nappies generators, potential parents, nursery employees)

The nappies generators are all those groups of residential or non-residential waste generators characterized by a daily use of nappies. Nappies are used mainly by babies not yet toilet-trained or by ill people (mainly elderly but also younger people). The nappies generators addressed by the actions of W4T are: families with newborns and nurseries in Seveso, Zamudio and Halandri, and hospices in Zamudio and Seveso. In the case of families, the main target of the sensitization actions of W4T will be the parents. About the nursery and the hospice, the actions must be aimed to employees but also to the managers in order to foster a strong commitment at the management level.

Public administration

Generally, the term Civil Service type organization comprising professional staff, endowed with economic and public materials, which implements the decisions taken by the government of a state. It consists of everything that makes it effective, officials and public buildings, among others. For this role, is the link between citizens and political power.

Waste collection operators (cleaning services at public administration, waste collector and truck drivers)

The waste collection process is comprised of a bunch of daily tasks that include personnel from both the waste collection companies and the public administration. On the one hand, truck drivers and operators will fulfil the service thanks to hardware and the tools they are provided with on the trucks. On the other hand, the service performance can be checked and improved (if needed) from the administration departments on both public and private (waste company) sides. Such improvements, together with the environmental harm decrease, can be carried on by means of hardware and software tools.

Waste Collection Company

Waste management includes all the activities and actions required to manage waste from its generation to its final treatment (collection, transportation, disposal or recycling and monitoring). The waste (gaseous, liquid, solid, etc.) is managed to avoid its adverse effect over human health and environment and, most of the time, to get resources from it. The management of municipal waste is general responsibility of the local government that typically entrust to a company all the waste management activities. This company in some cases deals with many more issues such as PAYT invoicing, waste and fleet monitoring including its optimization; hence will be a target group involved in the actions and the decision processes of W4T.

Technician

A technician is someone who is a nursery employee with technical skills or an employee of a technical company (such as Genentech) and is responsible for the appropriate operation of the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU). He has the responsibility to check if the equipment works properly, check and update the recording files of the WTU and inform the head of the nursery in any case. In

addition, he has to empty the bag filters of the WTU, load and empty the composter frequently to ensure its proper operation.

Regarding the dryer/shredder unit in Halandri, a worker will be trained to operate the unit. The training will be done by the supplier of the unit under the supervision on engineers (ENBIO-MUNICIPALITY OF HALANDRI). The operator will also work on the collection of bio waste, and thus must have an appropriate driving license.

Food waste manager (food waste recyclers and food waste re-users, basically in social kitchen)

Food waste recyclers. Dried bio waste will be distributed to:

- National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) Lab, where the characteristics of the product will be studied and identified. Further, a series of different solutions will be evaluated: production of liquid biofuel, biosorbent material, microbial fuel cells, pellet, livestock feed, compost.
- ENBIO, which is responsible for the production, evaluation and upgrade of biogas to be used in a truck.

TITAN AE (cement industry), which will evaluate the properties of the product as alternative fuel for its processes.

Food Waste “reusers” (Prevention)

NGO’s in collaboration with the municipality collect food which is edible but not able to be marketed (i.e. yesterday’s bread from bakeries) and distribute it to families which have been identified from the municipality as beneficiaries or to social kitchens.

Waste manager public bodies (policy makers and waste manager technicians)

The Waste Managers, typically part of Public Bodies, are responsible for waste management at the local, regional or national level. Strategies and decisions about how to manage waste are taken by policy makers both at the municipal and the regional/national level, by means of political or administrative guidelines or regulations. These decisions are also based on advices of waste management technicians such as external consultants etc. that are aware and expert on all the technical issues regarding the waste management. The policy makers can be different among EU countries, basically according to the national regulation and the transposition of EU Directives.

	ZAMUDIO	HALANDRI	SEVESO	CASCAIS
CITIZENS				
PRIMARY AND SECONDARY STUDENTS				
UNIVERSITARY STUDENTS				
SME (small <50 employees)				
SME (medium <250 employees)				
RESEARCHERS				
ASSOCIATIONS				
EDUCATIONAL CENTERES				
DOMESTIC GENERATOR				
TOURIST				
COMMERCIAL GENERATORS				
INDUSTRIAL GENERATORS				
FOOD WASTE GENERATORS				
NAPPIES GENERATORS				
PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION				
WASTE COLLECTION OPERATORS				
WASTE COLLECTION COMPANY				
TECHNICIAN				
FOOD WASTE MANAGER				
WASTE MANAGER PUBLIC BODIES				

Fig. 5 Target groups tackled in the Social Action Plan by pilot

5 Key messages

The main key messages identified by the pilots for the different social actions they are going to develop are:

GENERAL- WHOLE WASTE MANAGEMENT CHAIN

- In a **circular economy**, we keep products and materials in use for **as long as possible**, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate new products and materials at the end of each service life. We design out wasted energy, materials and pollution. **We achieve a more sustainable use of our resources.**
- **Resource management** is central to sustainable development and that the waste management sector has a crucial role to play in optimizing material and energy use within the circular economy. The **circular economy is an opportunity** for the waste management sector. It is a catalyst for new skills, innovation, knowledge and development; and will result in new technologies, business models and partnerships.
- If we **re-manufacture, reuse and recycle**, we can move to a circular economy, where waste is eliminated and resources are used in a more efficient and sustainable way*.

- The waste management sector **has the skills and knowledge** needed to facilitate the drive to a circular economy throughout the value chain.
- **Improvement of innovation capacity** and integration of **new knowledge and methodologies** in the area of waste management in urban environments.
- **Efficient** collection routes; use of more sustainable vehicles and correct driving habits; traffic data and street properties; new waste management strategies based on re-use of some waste (nappies, food wastes) reducing CO₂ generation in comparison with incineration.
- Waste4Think will set as main priority aspects of infrastructure, health and environment, integrating concerns on **conservation of nature and resources**, towards a strategic aim of a recycling and a **“green” society, promoting the prevention of waste and using the produced waste as a resource in a sustainable manner**, reducing negative environmental impacts in cities.
- The successful emergence of the circular economy calls for **research and development involving multiple disciplines**, cross-sector technologies, economic considerations and the natural and social sciences.
- All actors **in the value chain need to interact** and be involved **in the transition toward a circular economy** – designers, producers, manufacturers, consumers, policy makers, and the waste management sector. The waste management sector wants to engage proactively with all actors along the value chain.
- Europe, State Members and citizens can benefit economically and environmentally from making better use of those resources.
- Circular economy can be enhanced by developing and embracing new ways of behaviour, building new business models and learning from existing resource efficient businesses. New platforms for business development as well as including circular economy messages at all levels of education are needed to promote this.
- A more sustainable use of resources (water, land, energy, minerals, etc.) will also make us more resilient to unpredictable commodity prices in an uncertain future world and offer greater protections from rising and volatile energy prices.

PREVENTION & ECODESIGN

- **Promoting the prevention** of waste and using the produced waste as a resource in a sustainable manner **we can reduce negative environmental impacts in cities.**

- To **maximize the benefits and use of our resources**, products will need to be designed both to be more easily disassembled for material recovery, and also to incorporate more recycled content.
- **Social, environmental and economic benefits** could be achieved by preventing and reusing waste.

SEPARATE COLLECTION & RECYCLING

- All communities need to carefully manage the waste they produce. Recycling helps to **keep waste out of landfills** that otherwise will grow and reduce the amount of community space available for residential development, parks or commercial uses.
- Improvements in urban waste sorting, management costs or reduction of Greenhouse Gas emissions can be achieved, is in our hands.
- Source separation is mandatory to achieve high recycling rates of quality resources. Social, environmental and also economical benefits must be explained and, if possible, applied to final users (citizens, business...), for example applying PAYT systems.
- Further reductions in waste emissions could be supported through introduction of stronger levers, particularly **targeting household food waste**, which is likely to continue to be a major contributor to future landfill emissions. For example, households can be further encouraged to reduce waste arising and increase recycling efforts. Local authorities can increase provision of separate food waste collection services, which can further unlock potential for producing energy through anaerobic digestion. The Government should also consider bans on major sources of biodegradable waste (e.g. food and textiles) from landfill on a case-by case basis.
- The waste management sector's experience in developing and operating solutions for material and energy recovery as well as its everyday experience of facing the challenges of taking care of the residues of the linear economy will make a valuable contribution to this task.

A part from these general messages, specific ones have been developed for the different social actions and are described in the factsheet of each action.

6 Description of the ICT based tools

The following table includes a short description of the ICT based educational tools that are created in the framework of W4T and integrated in the different SA:

Type	Name	ACRO NIM	Short Description
Apps	Food App (R5)	FA	App to promote donation of food
	Local Trade App (R6) ¹	LTA	App to foster local trade and sustainable consumption. Merged with the Citizens App
	Citizens App (R7)	CA	App to provide citizens with information related to the waste collection system
Learning Materials (R8)	DP1 Prevention and reuse	DP1	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around prevention and reuse
	DP2 Source separation and recycling	DP2	Set or integration of STEAM lessons, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around source separation & recycling
	DP3 Home compost/ Food waste	DP3	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around Home compost & food waste in general
	DP4 Product Life Cycle	DP4	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around Life Cycle of products and services
	DP5 Waste Tax	DP5	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to increase knowledge around waste tax and PAYT
	DP6 Monitoring of waste generation	DP6	Set or integration of digital units, games and other related learning materials with the aim to help in waste monitoring at different levels (school, house, city...)
	MG1. 0WASTE	MG1	Tool for monitoring the waste/resource generation and the time evolution in an easy way.
	MG2. SUNFLOWER	MG2	Mobile game to discover the secrets of the best compost and keep your sunflower alive.

¹ In order to make it easier and to simplify the way to interact with citizens it has been decided to develop The Local Trade App as a part of the Citizen App. Therefore the Citizen App presents a bigger range of information what makes it more complete.

Type	Name	ACRO NIM	Short Description
	MG3. TREASURE MACHINE	MG3	Mobile game to show the real value of "waste". Aimed at explain circular economy in an easy way.
	MG4. WASTE-QUEST	MG4	"Gymkhana game" with specific challenges that can be set by each pilot or user
Serious Games	Ways2Sort (R9)	W2S	Educate mainly young children on the importance of sorting waste and how to sort waste.
	Ecodesign game (R10)	EDG	A half-explorative puzzle game where a player designs and produces different versions of a product according to different market demands.
	Virtual City game (R12)	VCG	Game to communicate the principles of circular economy
	Planning Game / Major's Table (R11) ²	PG	Players have to decide the waste management strategy for their own towns. They have 4 advisors that will give them different perspectives about the problem and their solutions.

² As it was considered easier to find through search engines, and also to be sell, the Planning Game it's now available in applications stores as Major's Table.

7 Environmental Education Program in Zamudio

7.1 Participation of the local groups on the project definition and monitoring (Z1) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

Promotion of the involvement and direct participation of the different target groups in the development of the project in Zamudio, through the local existing communication tools and different participated working groups.

This strategy includes the next actions and activities:

Z1.1 General presentations of the project to explain the whole strategy, objectives, involvement activities to be held in the municipality, etc. [↗](#)

Z1.2 Participation workshop: open “brain-storming” workshop to start talking about the objectives of W4T in the municipality, and to explain the main beliefs regarding waste management, etc. During the deployment, the team considered it more convenient to carry out workshops directly associated with the implementation of Pay As You Throw system. See more about PAYT participation process with citizens, industries and businesses (Z6.2, Z6.3, Z6.4): [↗](#)

Z1.3 Citizens science actions: activities developed with the aim of empowering citizens with practical experiences like containers location in the municipality and reflection around citizen’s habits or sustainable consumption at local level by local interviews to Zamudio’s commerce. [↗](#)

Z1.4 “Non Bota Zer” campaign (“where to throw away what”), through website, articles, information point. [↗](#)

Z1.5 Summer camp activities dedicated to sustainable waste management fostering. [↗](#)

All this action will be complemented with the publication of a monthly article in the municipal magazine about the progress of the pilot, the environmental issues they are working on, etc.

OBJECTIVES

- Socialize the project
- Search the complicity of the citizenship
- Empower the different target groups

PROMOTER

Zamudioko Udala-Ayuntamiento de Zamudio

EXECUTER

Zamudioko Udala-Ayuntamiento de Zamudio

Txorrieri Mancomunidad

External help

KEY MESSAGES

Communication is the basis of learning and knowledge. The more you communicate the activities and actions, people become more participatory. The changes involve everybody and everybody can actively participate to promote the best way to increase prevention and recycling

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Inhabitants of Zamudio				
Inhabitants of the valley of Txorierrri				
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
1. Human resources.				
1.1. Trainers or coaches for the working groups meetings				
1.2. Educators and informers for the surveys, etc.				
1.3. Other				
2. Equipment: for the presentations				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Municipal magazine, website, presentations, etc.				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z1.1				
Z1.2				
Z1.3	CA			
Z1.4	CA			
Z1.5				
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: November 2016				
End date: December 2019				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: Quantitative & Qualitative				
Means: surveys				
Results indicators to be calculated: Participation and Social Acceptance. See the annex 2				

7.2 Schools Campaign and activities (Z2) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

With the Campaigns at school's municipality want to:

- Z2.1 Present the learning materials to the teachers, in order to make the necessary final adaptations. Training teachers in the use of the learning modules and their tools. VirtualWare will coordinate the use of these materials with the teachers of each school. The campaigns that the municipality wants to promote must be coordinated with the application of didactic materials in the schools. [↗](#)
- Z2.2 Introduce self-composting to test on site treatment of bio waste, regarding this, teaching units about food waste and composting will be developed. They will start

working on it on the first trimester of 2017-18 school year. At schools, the composter will be managed by the schools themselves as a teaching project and the compost will be used in their vegetable garden. To use it correctly, it will be important to make a proper training with teachers and pupils. To do that, Zamudio municipality or Txorierri Municipalities association will hire an educator. ↗

- Z2.3 Promote the reduction of the single use light packaging. As a measure, Zamudio municipality will deliver bock'n'rolls among Zamudio Public School pupils (probably, it will be delivered among primary and secondary first courses, in order to repeat the same action next courses and reach to all pupils in few years), a competition between classes will be done in order to promote the use of these reusable packaging. The best group of users will receive a reward. ↗
- Z2.4 Improve selective collection and prevention teaching how to classify the waste correctly, identify waste as a resource, etc. VirtualWare will propose a specific learning material, while the municipality will foster actions related to the monitoring of the collection and generation, by making characterizations of the school bins (made by themselves). The main objective of it is to find out which items they throw away in the school and know if they are doing well. The sorting game will be used after this among the students. These actions are proposed for the second and third trimester of 17/18 school year. In order to know better how they are doing nowadays, municipality will start asking schools about their good habits works in this subject (baseline). ↗
- Z2.5 Dedicated workshops with schools. Workshops with teachers and students to use digital projects and games developed in the project to increase knowledge of good waste management. Several scholar activities has been developed in the frame of the project, e.g., candle workshop to promote recycling of cooking oil ↗, cooking course with leftovers to avoid food waste generation ↗, some apps and games were also presented in a fair dedicated to promote science among young people. ↗

OBJECTIVES

We want to promote zero waste at schools by improving their knowledge about waste.

Involve teachers, pupils and families to promote behavioural changes in e citizens to reduce waste and increase the rate of waste sorting.

Enhance prevention and separate collection demonstrating the benefits of sorting waste and learning about waste management and its impact in the environment.

PROMOTER

VirtualWare

Zamudio municipality

EXECUTER

Zamudio municipality or Txorierri community (by the hired educator)

VirtualWare

Teachers

KEY MESSAGES

<p>Make composting reduces the cost of the treatment of organic waste and also provides a good product for the land.</p> <p>Reduce single-use packaging.</p> <p>Reduce bulky fraction and save collection and transport money.</p> <p>Improve children waste generation and management behaviour.</p> <p>Prevent the generation of waste.</p> <p>Try to become a Zero Waste School.</p>				
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION: 4 SCHOOLS				
4 schools: not all schools will carry out all planned measures, because it depends on their next year programming.				
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
1. Human resources.				
1.1. Educators: 1 person in charge of the actions, training and coordination.				
1.2. Others: school teacher: they will help on the execution of campaigns.				
2. Equipment: screen, bins and containers, composter (Temperature + oxygen control), camera, scale, (budget 2000€/school). This equipment will be used for the monitoring of the measures implemented.				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Bock'n'rolls. Reward or incentive for other good practices. These are going to be distributed among the children that participate in the activities that are organized by the town hall every two weekend. The activities are divided according to the age of the assistant (children in play centre, teenager and the rest of inhabitants in eco-events or promotion campaigns).				
Other materials: 4 TV screen to present results and info of the project.				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z2.1		DP:1,2,3,4,5,6 MG: 1, 2, 3	W2S	
Z2.2		DP3. MG2	Sunflower	
Z2.3		DP:1,6. MG: 1,4	W2S	
Z2.4		DP		
Z2.5			Sunflower, W2S	
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: First trimester of 17-18 course.				
End date: Project end.				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				

Type: survey, learning analytics, waste characterization, etc.

Means:

Results: use the data collected about generation and selective collection for the subjects, use learning analytics, possible modification of the learning units at a second stage according to the results. After each action, we should fulfil the Social KPI reporting template, considering quantity and quality issues.

- Rate of separate collection at schools (%)
- Average kg/day per student
- Number of agreements established with educational centres to prevent waste
- Reduction of light packaging in schools (kg /students)
- Effective use of reusable packaging in schools (% of students)
- Number of school's centres that take part in the contest to prevent waste
- Number of centres with composting units
- Volume of the composting units (total)

EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE

Target groups: addressed to teachers and pupils of different ages, the same pupils can inform their families.

A close relation with teachers will be hold during the project.

7.3 Food waste prevention campaign (Z3) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

Involve all the possible agents responsible for food waste generation to (1) implement food wastage avoiding by behavioural campaigns, and (2) to identify new business. To reach these, next main actions are going to be carried out:

- **Z3.1 General campaign** introducing the impact of generation of avoidable food waste. Some general actions will be included in this action, as an **information point** in the downtown in order to promote eco-solutions and help citizens in the implementation of these actions, the edition of a decalogue of good practices in food management to avoid food wastage, information point in some local popular events with a photo call using items and information related with food wastage (the main objective is to change inhabitants' behaviour regarding ugly or useless food), Christmas campaign to prevent senseless and huge food purchases. [↗](#)
- **Z3.2. Creative cooking course** will be taught by a well-known cook in the public installations (txoko) of the municipality. The assistants will use food waste in order to prepare different meals. A video of the event and, another about how they have prepared the dish, is expected to be distributed at the end of the event through mass media (EITB, the post, TV, Youtube Waste4Think Channel). It is planned to make 2-3 courses, and the first one, it is going to be held by the first semester of 2018. [↗](#)
- **Z3.3 The food app** will be implemented in the large food waste generators. The aim is

to create surplus alerts and potential users come to surplus alert point in order to take the food. Additionally, the registration of food donated by schools to the cooperative social kitchens will be done. As the Z3.4 was organized the pilot decided to assign efforts to enforce this other initiative and proposed the app as a way to register and obtain statistics about the amount and environmental impacts of the non-generated food waste.

- Z3.4 Zamudio municipality has sign an agreement with Aunar non-profitable organization. With this agreement, Zamudio municipality will support (paying Aunar services) the re-introduction of catering food which would otherwise be thrown away, and the distribution of that food among 10 families who need this help. These citizens are selected by municipality social technician. Aunar will be the responsible of providing breakfast, lunch and dinner meals for the whole week, and at least, during a year. If they make a bad use of this service, Aunar will tell it to the municipality, and they will define together if they must change the family grantee. [↗](#)

Finally, in the Citizen app it will appear some good practices related with the food purchase and citizens will have the chance to find out trades that have implemented some eco-solutions (km0, ecological or bulk products, for example).

OBJECTIVES

Avoid food waste generation in the different targets: domestic and large generators

Prevent food wastage.

Raise awareness against the food wastage.

Promote use of food which would otherwise be wasted.

PROMOTER

Zamudio

EXECUTER

Zamudio

FDeusto

KEY MESSAGES

Too much food waste is generated and we can avoid its generation with simple actions and good planning of daily meals.

There are better management ways for bio waste.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Large food waste generators (supermarkets, restaurants, caterings) will be able to use the Food App and promote the measures related with the food wastage.

Citizens in general: information and awareness campaigns, creative cooking courses, use of the food app.

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers. Tasks and contents: A well-known cook will give the course in the txokos

1.2 Educator. Tasks and contents: inform people and promote food wastage social campaigns, explain the use of the food app, ...

1.3. Other

2. Equipment: cooking material, kitchen (txokos). Information point material.

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Leaflets, municipal magazine, photo call and some other materials which will be defined when the Christmas campaign is decided.

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z3.1	FA			
Z3.2	FA	DP1		
Z3.3	FA			

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION START DATE:

Start date:

Aunar project: March 2018

Food app and characterization system: 2018

General campaigns: End of 2018

End date: Project end

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Type: waste analysis, number of users

Means:

Results indicators to be calculated

1. Reduction of food waste

2 Increase in the percentage of food waste separately collected

3 User: apps, courses

Other: See the annex 2

EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE

Target groups: citizens and large food waste generators (supermarkets, restaurants and caterings).

Information provided: KPIs

Channels used: municipal magazine, citizen app, street educator.

7.4 Commercial Activities Campaign (Z4) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

Not only the residual waste must be reduced, but also the lightweight packaging stream has a huge margin for reduction. Therefore, three main campaigns are going to be implemented in Zamudio through the commercial activities.

- Z4.1 Diagnosis. Firstly, it is important to know what is the local trades starting point and, to what eco-solutions and campaigns want to join. For that, a survey is going to be done, trying to know what type of products they sell, and what type of eco-solutions have implemented in their trades. And we will present the measures which municipality wants to promote, such as, the use of tuppens, reusable bags, and other incentives. If they help on it, the information will be uploaded on de citizen app. In the citizen app, also will be able to be read some good practices related with the food purchase and citizens will have the chance to find out those trades that they implement proposing eco-solutions (km0, ecological or bulk products). [↗](#)
- Z4.2 Tupper campaign. Municipality will promote the use of the “Tupper” in fish markets and butchers. Two tuppens are going to be distributed to each home, one for fish and other for butchery. While citizens used them, local businesses gave them different labels that could be accumulated and then exchanged for a kit consisting of other items such as an isothermal bag or a reusable sandwich wrapper as an incentive. In order to simplify the understanding of these interventions, the delivery of tuppens and reusable bags was registered jointly (Z4.2 & Z4.3). [↗](#)
- Z4.3 Reusable bags for local market are already running but it will be reinforced, with the distribution of a new reusable bags campaign especially dedicated to substitute the superlight bags for fruits and vegetables. They will be given to people who use previously distributed reusable bags. This monitoring will be done by the local traders. In order to simplify the understanding of these interventions, the delivery of tuppens and reusable bags was registered jointly. [↗](#)
- Z4.4 Citizen App campaign. The Citizen App will be promoted at local level to foster local sustainable consumption and good habits in terms of purchasing and consumption decision making. [↗](#)

Z4.2 and Z4.3 will be developed together with a process of gamification to assure the best results in terms of new habits promotion and maintenance of these new habits in time.

OBJECTIVES

Reduction of the amount of lightweight packaging for domestic uses.

Promotion of ecolabel goods, prevention habits and local commercial activities.

Promotion of the Citizen App among inhabitants.

PROMOTER

Zamudio

EXECUTER

Zamudio				
KEY MESSAGES				
<p>Promote best practices to reduce the impact of citizens purchase habits.</p> <p>Explain of the benefits of habits changes, in terms of social, environmental and economic impacts.</p> <p>Packaging could be reduced, so the impacts of producing, collecting and land filling also.</p> <p>Promote those good practices which are doing local trades.</p> <p>To give the chance to change citizen's "non-ecological" habits.</p>				
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION				
<p>Zamudio inhabitants</p> <p>Commercial Activities</p>				
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
<p>1. Human resources.</p> <p>1.1. Municipality technician: to contact with local trades and make the first approach.</p> <p>1.2. Educator. Tasks and contents: Educators to promote the use of the tupperware, reusable bags and answer citizens and business doubts.</p> <p>1.3. Municipality will rent a small centre place as information and promotion point. It will be a "good habits of consumption" information point and campaigns promotion point.</p> <p>1.4. Tupperware and reusable bags.</p> <p>1.5. Stick for trading partner.</p>				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Leaflets and municipal magazine.				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z4.1	CA			
Z4.4	CA			
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: last trimester of 2017.				
End date: project end.				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: quality and quantity analysis				
Means: surveys and results analysis				
Indicators:				
<p>1. Reduction of light packaging: how much lightweight packaging have trades saved (€ or units).</p> <p>2. Real usage of the tupperware and reusable bags. How many people use it during the campaign and how much in the coming months (a comparative through a questionnaire)</p>				

to traders).
3. Business published in the Citizen App and app visits.
Other. See annex 2.
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: general citizen, local trades
Information provided: level of light-weight packaging reduction
Channels used: information point, municipal magazine, citizen app
When: after the data of the start of the campaign, quarterly assessment.

7.5 Composting (Z5)

DESCRIPTION

Composting will be promoted in the framework of the project, in schools specially, but also among inhabitants, local trades and enterprises.

Regarding schools, composting will be done in the framework of the school campaigns explained previously (see Z2.2: school campaigns .

- Z5.1 The community composting plant will be used for bio waste generated in Zero Waste Events and for those citizens who want to throw there their bio waste. There will be 6 modules, 2 for events and the others, for inhabitants.

In the first case, the organic waste will be sorted by the event organizers, and collection and transport enterprise will take it to community composting plant place (municipality ground). After that, a municipality worker will make the mix and will look after it. To do it well, municipality worker will make a training course.

Regarding to the use by the citizens, they will need to sign an agreement, and before starting use it, they must do a training course. After it, they will have the permission to open the door to enter to the composting plant.

- Z5.2 Increase of the knowledge about compost as key message to understand circular economy, food waste cycle, etc. It includes some activities where compost will be distributed. For example, compost will be used by the gardening service for Zamudio municipality parks and gardens. Also, municipality will distribute the compost from Zero Waste Events among participants of **the balcony flower competition**. Users of the community composting will be allowed to pick up some compost also.

OBJECTIVES

Promotion of onsite treatment of bio waste.

Improve sorting rates.

Reduce Urban Solid Waste numbers and cost.

PROMOTER

Zamudio															
EXECUTER															
Zamudio															
KEY MESSAGES															
Bio waste is a valuable material to be recycled and obtain compost, necessary to maintain the soil productivity. The bio waste cycle is an example of circular economy. Reducing waste, we reduce also the costs of waste management.															
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION															
Schools Citizens Zero Waste Events organizations. Local trades and enterprises															
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION															
1. Human resources.															
1.1. Trainers: Trainers to teach composting training courses.															
1.2. Municipality worker: to manage composting plant after a ZWE. Educators: to promote the use among citizens and business.															
1.3. Other: Composting plants, and the rest of tools or sources which are necessary to compost properly (pending on the type of composting plants which finally will be bought)															
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS															
Composting plants monitoring systems (schools and others). Promotion material (leaflets and municipal magazine).															
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED															
See more details in Annex 0															
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>STRATEGY CODE</th> <th>APPS</th> <th>LEARNING MATERIALS</th> <th>SERIOUS GAMES</th> <th>OTHER</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Z5.1</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Z5.2</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER	Z5.1					Z5.2				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER											
Z5.1															
Z5.2															
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION															
Start date: 06-24-2017 (community composting plant) 10-01-2017 (school composting plants)															
End date: Project end JUL 2019															
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS															
Type: quantitative & qualitative Means: scale (before and after to be composted) Data-set of the number of people or business joint to the composting.															

Weight machine or volume reference (each module). Municipality worker should fulfil a template about incidents in the composting plant (quantity and quality of the bio waste and the compost).
Indicators: Properly sorting (visual inspection before throwing waste in the composting plant). Weight or volume of generated organic waste and composted material. People trained Others (see annex 2)
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: citizens, schools, commercials
Information provided: level of reduction and useful information to join to the composting.
Channels used: citizen app, information points and municipal and a supralocal municipality administration magazines.
When: quarterly assessment.

7.6 PAYT- New collection scheme with monitoring use of containers system (Z6)

DESCRIPTION

In Zamudio, the waste collection system will change by locking some of the containers and identifying the users in order to lose “anonymity” and promote responsibility. In this sense, a monitoring system for the main waste streams will be deployed: residual waste and light packaging (id and chamber), paper-cardboard, glass, reusable, organic waste and domestic oils (id). The system works with the citizen card that must be swiped previous to unlock the bin.

After a period of monitoring (when some behavioural changes will be tested), the PAYT scheme will be introduced. The PAYT system will be implemented for commercials, industry and household activities. It should be necessary to explain carefully which changes will involve the new PAYT system proposal, so a lot of actions will be developed:

- Z6.1 General information about PAYT. Zamudio’s town hall will explain what PAYT is in all the participatory sessions held in Zamudio. Will also take advantage of all the times that there is talk about waste, to explain and introduce PAYT. As well several articles are going to be published in the local magazine. Dedicated information will be introduced also through participatory workshops.
- Z6.2 Citizens participation process. As we made a survey and the project presentation, municipality invited inhabitants to take part in the following participation process. Those people, who want to take part, will be called to ensure their assistance.

Municipality wants a heterogeneous participation group, so they will also contact some people who probably are against the change.

Three meetings will be organized to talk about the following topics: monitoring system, the location of containers, and the PAYT scheme. Municipality will hire an expert enterprise services (in participation process), which will be responsible of streamlining these meetings. These meetings will start with major's briefly presentation of the theme, and after that, we will start working in small groups. The meeting will finish putting the main conclusion in common and fulfilling a satisfaction survey. Enterprise must make a summary and share it with us, to distribute it among participators and inhabitants who want to know more about the process (uploading the summary on the website and publishing an article in local magazine). [↗](#)

- Z6.3 Commercial participation process. A dedicated participatory workshop will be done with local commerce to explain PAYT system and application to economical activities, to achieve a better definition of the PAYT system to be applied, changes needed to assure the best service adapted to the needs of the commerce, etc. [↗](#)
- Z6.4 Industrial participation process. Another participation process will be done with industrial system in Zamudio, to inform them about Waste5Think and adapt PAYT to their specific needs. [↗](#)
- Z6.5. Door-to-door visits: before start applying the new PAYT system, both in the pilot and in the whole community, the educators will go home by home explaining the system, trying to be sure that has been properly understood. [↗](#)
- Z6.6 Information points: the main idea is spreading carefully all novelties of the collection and payment system. Municipality will rent a property in the downtown in order to answer all doubts and start and promote social campaigns about the PAYT system (and others). Municipality will also put an information point in popular local events. [↗](#)

OBJECTIVES

Introduce a fair method for waste tax rewarding virtuous citizens (PAYT).

Increase the rate of separated waste.

Spreader a double message, residual waste can be minimized by both increasing recycling and implementing prevention actions.

Try to involve all citizens in the monitoring and PAYT definition.

KEY MESSAGES

Waste prevention and separate collection is our responsibility.

PAYT is a method to promote fairness. With the introduction of PAYT, some users (the more virtuous ones) may experience a decrease in their tax but some others may also experience an increase.

PAYT aims at transparency. In the invoice citizens will get customized information of their production, economic balances and benefits of recycling etc.

The introduction of PAYT should be participative; every citizen must be aware of its advantages

this change and bad behaviours like littering will be punished.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Citizens: explanation of how works the system (traditional campaigns and training days)
Industries: what changes will involve the new PAYT system proposal

PROMOTER

Zamudio

EXECUTER

Zamudio and internal-partner

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. To streamline the participation process. Tasks and contents: they will be responsible of streamlining all meetings and make a summary of the main conclusions of each meeting.

1.2. Educators: for door-to door visits and information points. Tasks and contents: Explain to citizens how works the system and promote social action campaign related with PAYT and others social actions.

1.3. Other

2. Equipment: Information point furniture, video and sound system, municipal cultural house, leaflets and website place.

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Website, leaflets and municipal magazine

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z6.1	CA	DP5	VCG MT	
Z6.2	CA			
Z6.3	CA			
Z6.4	CA			
Z6.5	CA			
Z6.6	CA			

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: Previous preparation actions February 2017

May 2017: participation process

Last quarter of 2018: shadow invoices

2019: PAYT
End date: September 2019.
Since some of the planned tasks related with providers and other burocratic aspects were delayed, so did the arrival of the new containers, and the implementation of the shadow invoices. PAYT scheme will be fully implemented by April 2020
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS
Type: waste analysis, focus groups, surveys, system data
Means: Quality surveys and meetings summaries
Results indicators to be calculated
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of HH participating Number of users participating Number of alerts for incorrect use of the bins Others (see annex 2)
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: general citizen
Information provided: level of prevention and separate collection, level of inappropriate items in bins, level of satisfaction
Channels used: municipal magazine, citizen app, website
When: quarterly assessment

7.7 Zero waste ecosystem (Z7) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

In Zamudio the transition to two zero waste ecosystems will be tested: town hall and schools. Schools will reach to be a Zero Waste Ecosystem carrying out the learning materials and the school campaigns proposed before (see Z2: School campaigns). The main objective is to demonstrate how, implementing school campaigns and changing habits, they will reduce the waste generation.

Other Zero Waste ecosystems are foreseen to be developed in the framework of the project:

- Z7.1 Town Hall pilot. The town hall will become a Zero Waste Ecosystem applying different measures. To do it well, we will copy some good practices examples. For that, some internal partners will make a review of best practices in Zero Waste Ecosystems around the world, and after that, we will implement the most appropriate ones. [↗](#)
- Z7.2 Industries. We would like to enrol some local industries as a Zero Waste Ecosystems. [↗](#)

OBJECTIVES

Transition towards zero waste ecosystems.

Reduce the amount of waste produced and increase the rate of separated waste in households, industrial area and schools.
Sensitize other citizens about the possibilities to change their behaviour in managing their waste, with a minimal impact in everyday life.
Inform about the produced benefits to the all society and to the environment.
Normalize Zero Waste Ecosystems requirements so as to involve new administration or industries.
PROMOTER
Zamudio
EXECUTER
Zamudio and Internal-partners
KEY MESSAGES
Local administration must change its behaviour regarding waste generation.
Waste production could be reduced to almost zero, through some behaviours that can even adopted by citizens at home (e.g. avoiding the purchase of disposable products, optimizing the separate collection of waste, etc.).
Learn at school that every resource is useful.
Resources must be optimized.
Everyone should take part to get these goals.
Changing our habits is not so difficult, with great benefits for environment and society.
It is important to do it too in industry environments.
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION
Civil servants: how to manage the waste in the workplace: alternative behavioural ways such as having its ceramic cup for coffee instead of plastics cups...
Pupils of schools: get the reason of why generate so much waste at class and identify alternative options.
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION
1. Human resources.
1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents
1.2. Educator. Tasks and contents: they will be there in order to work with schools in the implementation of social action campaign (see Z1: school campaigns).
1.3. Other: school's teachers
2. Equipment: screens to monitor the indicators and other possible equipment (see Z1: school campaigns), other equipment for the Town Hall and local industries.
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS
School's blogs, leaflets and municipal magazine
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z7.1				
Z7.2				

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: September 2017

End date: June 2019

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Type: waste analysis

Means: Direct measurements

Results indicators to be calculated

1. Reduction of the waste generation
2. Increase sorting collection
3. Low levels of inappropriate items in each recycling bin.

Other: number of zero waste ecosystems, number or workers involved, etc. (see annex 2)

EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE

Target groups: general citizen, children at schools, workers

Information provided: level of reduction and separate collection

Channels used: municipal magazine, citizen app, municipal portal

When: monthly evolution of the generation. Screen will show the results of the monitorization.

7.8 Zero waste events (Z8) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

In Zamudio several popular meals are taken during the year. Municipality wants to turn these popular meals in Zero Waste Events. In this sense, municipality will get in contact with different organizations in order to discuss which measures will be implemented finally. Town hall proposal contains next measures,

Reusable tableware: the main goal is to get use to reusable tableware. The tableware owner will be the municipality and organizations will ask for using it. Knowing that it will not be easy implementing it from the beginning, we will start using biodegradable tableware.

Sorting waste collection: there will be a few collection points with the main waste streams in order to foster recycling fractions. These points will be clearly explained, using fraction-

name stickers and drop banners.

Information points and campaigns: it has planned to have an educator promoting and helping people to sort waste well. This point may also be used to foster other social campaigns or project's solutions (e.g. sorting game/planning game competition, raffle among people who sort the waste properly).

The Zero Waste events are split in three types of events depending on their specific characteristics:

- Z8.1 "Day" festivals: fairs, demonstrations, running race. [↗](#)
- Z8.2 Popular meals. Organization of Zero Waste Events in Popular meals [↗](#)
- Z8.3 Night festivals: concerts, drinking bars. [↗](#)

OBJECTIVES

Transition towards Zero Waste Events.

Reduce the amount of waste produced in popular local events.

Sensitize the citizenship and the organizing associations about the proper management of waste, aimed to reduce its production and to better perform the separate collection, and, more in general, about environment impacts of everyday life.

Foster social campaigns and communication actions.

Show project results, games and apps.

PROMOTER

Zamudio

EXECUTER

Internal-partner

KEY MESSAGES

One use resources are useless.

Reusable resources can reduce waste generation, save money and be more sustainable.

Increasing the separate collection can save money and be more sustainable.

Waste production in Zero Waste Events could be reduced to almost zero using resources properly, such as, using reusable tableware.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Citizens attending to the event.

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.2. Educator. Tasks and contents: Educator will explain alternative behaviours, promote social campaigns and help people to take care about waste generation in this type of popular.

1.3. Other

2. Equipment: screens, electricity, table, tableware, cleaning service, community composting plant, containers, drop banners, ...

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Leaflets, municipal magazine and citizen app

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 03				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z8.1			W2S / VCG / PG	
Z8.2			W2S / EDG	
Z8.3				
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: June 17 (all life of the project) 2 meals a year				
End date: Project end				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: waste analysis				
Means: reduction of unsorted waste, organic waste and packaging, increase of separate collection rate. To achieve and verify these goals it's fundamental to measure the performances of each Eco-events related to the number of participants. The data have to be then processed and stored in the Municipal data-base.				
Results indicators to be calculated				
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduction of the waste generation 2. Increasing of the separate collection 3. Comparison with previous popular meals 				
Other: number of public Ecoevents with reusable dishes, number of Ecoevents with food cooked with food surplus, etc. See annex 2.				
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE				
Target groups: Zamudio's inhabitants				
Information provided: level of reduction and separate collection				
Channels used: municipal magazine, citizen app, municipal information point				
When: after a popular meal (comparing with previous meals).				

7.9 Miscellaneous (Z9) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

During the project, the municipality will promote more social campaigns that are not directly related to the purposes of the Project, but that support the achievement of the same objectives. Therefore, it has been considered important to introduce this section of general campaigns. Among those planned are,

- Z9.1 Quiz: is a competition between children that seeks to promote the use of Euskera. It is a quiz of different topics. In the next course will introduce subjects related to

recycling, so that while you are promoting the use of Euskera, you are learning things related with recycling or other related issues. [↗](#)

- Z9.2 Halloween: Zamudio want to foster a different Halloween. Our history says that Basque people, because of the relationship with the Celts, celebrated a souls' festival, where people disguised themselves. So, municipality has proposed making a parade in the streets, in which the costumes are made with recyclable materials, and the candles, with used domestic oil. [↗](#)
- Z9.3 Promotion of the domestic oil container: local magazines will publish a new announcing the oil collection numbers and inviting citizens to recycle it. To do this, the man community will distribute 200 plastic boats of 5 liters per municipality, as an incentive for those citizens who want to start, or continue, recycling oil. [↗](#)
- Z9.4 Menstrual cup promotion. Promotion and distribution of menstrual cups. [↗](#)

OBJECTIVES

Introduce good practices and show recycling as a positive thing.
Promote knowledge related with project aims.

KEY MESSAGES

Waste prevention and separate collection is our responsibility.
Increasing the separate collection can save money and be more sustainable.
Reusable resources can reduce waste generation, save money and be more sustainable.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Citizens

PROMOTER

Zamudio

EXECUTER

Zamudio and internal-partner

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.
 - 1.1. Trainers or educators. People who participate in different organizations which take part in each action.
 - 1.3. Other: civil servant who foster each action.
2. Equipment: materials needed to organize these campaigns (pending on be defined)

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Website, municipal and Municipalities association magazine

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z9.5			VCG	

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: previous work February 2017 (contacts between politicians and municipality and a supralocal municipal administration technician)

End date: project ends October 2019

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Type: metrics, focus groups, surveys

Means: Direct measurements

Results indicators to be calculated

Number of participants

Municipality should think of any quality indicator.

EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE

Target groups: Citizens

Information provided: a review of the social action

Channels used: Local and county magazine, and websites

When: Every new action

Fig. 6 FORECAST: Zamudio's social actions forecast

8 Environmental Education Program in Halandri

8.1 Educational Centers activities (H1) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

- H1.1 Vocational School The municipality will organize a series of seminars and actions at high-schools (12-15 years old) directed at students. During 20-25 weeks, students will have a dedicated time around 1.5hs, after school classes, to work on these issues. The learning materials will be used and also some other additional activities as real composting and sorting, visits to treatment plants, monitoring and characterization, etc. In the vocational school, they are going to work also on the biodiesel in a more technical point of view. [↗](#)
- H1.2 Gymnasium. Other activities will be developed in other Halandri schools using some of the Ecosolutions set up during the project. Specially, they are going to work on composting at school as the municipality will be deploying the new food waste collection. [↗](#)
- H1.3 Summer Camp Activities [↗](#)

OBJECTIVES

To gain the interest of students in the concepts of waste management, prevention, recycling and sorting at the source, and to promote these concepts in their families.

To educate students and promote behavioural changes in order to increase the rate of waste sorting and cover the costs derived from the management.

PROMOTER

Municipality of Halandri

EXECUTER

Internal-partner and external (Tba)

KEY MESSAGES

Waste is a resource, not garbage. If we re-manufacture, reuse and recycle, we can move to a circular economy, where waste doesn't exist and resources are used in a more efficient and sustainable way.

Waste reduction has benefits for environment, saves money for the citizens and generates green jobs and green incomes for economy. To reduce the generation of waste on its origin thanks to prevention campaigns and cooperative activities.

The assimilation of the different recycling methods.

Each individual and/or organization is responsible for the waste he/she produces

Others: zero waste systems and circular economy concepts, realization of the benefits & feasibility of waste sorting at the source

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Students and teachers

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: Training for teachers

1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents: Specific units are to be incorporated in the (optional) environmental education program carried out in a particular secondary school, including monitoring and analysis of waste composition, composting and alternative use of food waste (following the eco-solutions developed in Waste4Think), reuse of waste and life cycle analysis. In addition, an activity regarding biodiesel production from used frying oil is to be carried out in a vocational school.

1.3. Other

2. Equipment: computers and mobile devices. Composting units with monitoring equipment in all Halandri schools, 3 bin system for recyclables in all schools. Biodiesel equipment in a vocational school.

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Leaflets and website

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
H1.1		DP1,2,3,4,6 MG1,2,3,4		
H1.2		DP1,2,3,4,6 MG1,2,3,4	W2S	
H1.3				

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: November 2017

End date: September of 2019 (feedback on the results)

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Type: number of students, waste analysis at schools, composting results in all schools

Means: scale, composting units with monitoring (temperature, moisture etc)

Results indicators to be calculated

1. Number of students involved

2. Usage of apps in the following weeks

3. Feedback from families

Other: waste generation, waste separated at source, compost produced. See annex 2.

EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE

Target groups: students, parents, teachers

Information provided: reports on the actions.

Channels used: teachers, parents associations

When: tba

8.2 Actions at Technical University (H2)

DESCRIPTION

- **H2.1 Ecodesign module introduction.** Before using the Ecodesign game, a dedicated work will be done with the students of chemical engineering. They are going to work in groups working on ecodesign concept and developing specific projects applying what they have learnt to some products and services. Some of the information developed will be used in the game.
- **H2.2 Use of the Ecodesign game** to teach about how the decisions the industrial designers make at the beginning influences on the impact of the whole life cycle in terms of waste, energy, emissions, water and raw materials consumption, etc.

OBJECTIVES

Impart knowledge to students with the technology

To make possible a bottom up strategy in which citizen and scholars are the main actors

Sensitize the future designers in ecodesign

PROMOTER

Prof. of the University (Department of Chemical Engineering)

EXECUTER

Internal-partner (Municipality of Halandri /NTUA/UPATRAS)

KEY MESSAGES

In a circular economy, we keep products and materials in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate new products and materials at the end of each service life. We design out wasted energy, materials and pollution. We achieve a more sustainable use of our resources.

The replacement of raw materials for making a product (such as nappies and coffee cups) that are based on fossil resources by renewable resources, such as biomass, reduces the impact on climate change (CO₂ emissions). In addition, the replacement of non-renewable energy sources by renewable energy sources, such as bio fuels, also improves significantly the sustainability aspects of manufacturing.

Bio fuels are cleaner fuels; they produce fewer emissions on burning. Since bio fuels can be made from renewable resources, they cause less pollution. Release lower levels of carbon dioxide and other emissions when burnt. Although the production of bio fuels creates carbon dioxide as a by-product, it is frequently used to grow the plants that will be converted into the fuel.

Engagement to main principles of circular economy.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

University students

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. 1 Trainer				
1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents				
1.3. Other				
2. Equipment: computers, etc.				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
-				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
H2.1				
H2.2			EDG	
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: 1/02/2018				
End date: 30/09/2019				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: number of students trained				
Means: report with comments by each participant				
Results indicators to be calculated				
1. Number of classes using the ecodesign game or other tools				
2. Number of students trained at University				
Other: See annex 2				
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE				
Target groups: university students				
Information provided: number of participants, comments on the use of the game				
Channels used: questionnaire				
When: at the end of the action.				

8.3 Food separate collection and treatment (H3)

DESCRIPTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H3.1 Initial seminars and campaign. The objective is to search participants for the pilot and explain the benefits of the new collection. The municipality will organize a series of seminars directed at the citizens who will volunteer to select kitchen bio waste.
OBJECTIVES
To familiarize the participating citizens with the municipality's waste management system, waste management concepts and innovations.
To train participating citizens on the Waste4Think apps and tools.
To encourage participants to become agents of peer to peer learning in their neighbourhoods.
To promote bio waste source separation.
PROMOTER
Municipality of Halandri
EXECUTER
Internal-partner and external (Tba)
KEY MESSAGES
Waste is a commodity, not garbage. If we re-manufacture, reuse and recycle, we can move to a circular economy, where waste is eliminated and resources are used in a more efficient and sustainable way
Bio waste cycle: a good separation at source is key to obtain good products
Food waste may be used as raw material for making compost, bio fuels etc. while its diversion from land filling has significant environmental impact and helps comply with the EU directive.
Each individual and/or organization is responsible for the waste he/she produces

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION				
Participating citizens & their neighbourhoods				
Municipality employees				
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
1. Human resources.				
1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: Seminars will be organized with experts from the W4T partners who will explain the collection system, its adaptations during the previous months, and will train the participating citizens in the use of the various apps and tools.				
1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents				
1.3. Other				
2. Equipment: educational material, sound system & presentation equipment, examples of the tools and apps.				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
10000 leaflets, magnet, questionnaire, website and Facebook groups.				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
H3.1				
H3.2			EDG	
H3.3	CA		VCG – MT	
H3.4	CA		VCG - MT	
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: February of 2017 (communication with citizens to get feedback on the collection system)				
End date: September of 2019 (feedback on the results)				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: number of participants/number of volunteers, feedback in the following weeks.				
Characterization of the product.				
Means: to compare the quality and the quantity of the product at the beginning and at the end of the campaign.				
Results indicators to be calculated				
1. Number of participants				
2. Usage of apps in the following weeks				
3. Adaptation of participating citizens to the solutions of the collection system				

(satisfaction)
4. Quantity/Quality of product
Other: See annex 2
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: participating citizens
Information provided: comments on the collection system, comments on the apps, and comments on the ease of use of sorting at the source, comments on the diffusing strategy itself
Channels used: direct contact with citizens by electronic means, social media
When: periodically, i.e. every 4-6 months. Also, "on demand" communication of the users will be available through telephone and internet.

8.4 Commercial Activities Campaign (H4)

DESCRIPTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H4.1 Citizens science. Some actions of citizen's science will be done in order to identify the position of the containers and to identify them using special QR codes with essential information about how to separate correctly, the destination of the material, and other useful data from the city. Additionally, food waste collection is fostered in some supermarkets.
OBJECTIVES
Increase the offer of best products and services towards prevention of environmental impact in general, and waste prevention and recycling in particular
Promoting a cleaner environment especially in the downtown area
Fostering a better understanding of waste-generation prevention and recycling actions.
PROMOTER
Municipality
EXECUTER
Internal-partner (Municipality of Halandri)
KEY MESSAGES
In a circular economy, we keep products and materials in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate new products and

materials at the end of each service life. We design out wasted energy, materials and pollution. We achieve a more sustainable use of our resources.				
Consumers can prevent waste and reduce their environmental impact by choosing better options in their daily purchases				
Local commerce can differentiate from other big activities and get benefits from being environmentally friendly				
Each individual and/or organization is responsible for the waste he/she produces				
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION				
Local shops (restaurants/ coffee shops and commercial shops), Specially the 185 shops in the city centre.				
Citizens				
Municipalities				
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
1. Human resources.				
1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents				
1.2. Educators and informers. 1-2 educators visiting the shops				
1.3. We will consider recognition and advertisement of local shops that comply with proper waste handling aspects through granting an ECOLABEL. The shops will be provided with stickers. They will also be listed in the Municipality site and will be included in citizen app.				
2. Equipment				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
200 leaflets and 10 posters				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
H4.1	CA			
H4.2	FA CA			
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: 1/02/2018				
End date: 30/09/2019				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: Number of participants				
Means: Report with comments by each participant.				
Results indicators to be calculated				
1. Number of participants (local shops)				

2. Satisfaction with the tools

Other: see annex 2

EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE

Target groups: Citizens, local commerce

Information provided: number of participants, tips to be “environmentally friendly”

Channels used: questionnaires

When: periodically.

8.5 Collection of nappies (H5) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

H5.1 **Contact with nappies producers** to make them participate to the pilot with nappies treatment. [↗](#)

H5.2 **Start of the collection & treatment.** Virtual operation of the Waste Treatment Unit in relation to typical daily routine of the nursery. [↗](#)

H5.3 **Feedback actions to participants** [↗](#)

OBJECTIVES

Training purposes of involved employees

Acquaintance of nurseries

PROMOTER

Municipality/Head of nursery

EXECUTER

Municipality of Halandri

KEY MESSAGES

In a circular economy, we keep products and materials in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate new products and materials at the end of each service life. We design out wasted energy, materials and pollution. We achieve a more sustainable use of our resources.

Nappies could be recycled and get new useful products from them.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Nurseries

Municipality

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION**1.** Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: train the nursery employee. 1 trainer

1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents

1.3. Other

2. Equipment: treatment unit, bins

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Leaflets and posters				
W2S ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
H5.1				
H5.2				
H5.3				
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: 1/02/2018				
End date: 30/09/2019				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: Number of participants				
Means: Report with comments by each participant				
Results indicators to be calculated				
1. Number of participants				
2. Nappies that end up in the waste treatment unit as percentage of total generated nappies on a daily basis				
Other:				
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE				
Target groups: Nursery heads & employees				
Information provided: number of participants, comments on the performance of the waste treatment unit as a result of the training using the planning game				
Channels used: email				
When: 2 months after the first implementation of the action and at the end of the action.				

		2016												2017												2018												2019											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
		Use case analysis						M1	Preparatory Actions												M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test						M4	Full Test						M5							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42						
Halandri Pilot																																																	
H1 Educational Centers activities	sep-17																																																
H2 Actions at the technical university	feb-18																																																
H3 Foodwaste separate collection	feb-17																																																
H4 Commercial Activities campaign	feb-18																																																
H5 nappies collection	feb-18																																																

Fig. 7 FORECAST: Halandri Social Actions calendar

9 Environmental Education Program in Seveso

9.1 Citizens' sensitization. An innovative "Funny door to door sensitization on residual waste" (SE1) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

Starting from the indications received by the Municipality of Seveso about the "critical subjects and places" in order to improve the waste collection, Legambiente will set up a team with a small vehicle that will carry out sensitization actions to explain mistakes and solutions in waste separation in an informal way, with music and performances.

After the recruitment of Funny door to door team, in parallel with the training activity, the Funny door to door team will plan the initiatives, tools, performances, media, check lists, materials linked to the project actions (tool box for the team) and design of communication materials. To do that, Legambiente will take into account the existing ones and the specific warnings of the municipality about critical situations in foreign communities. Legambiente will use a specific vehicle, with W4T logo, for its activities. Firstly, a press conference to launch the project has been organized for citizens in order to let them know about the aims of "Funny door to door", the foreseen actions and the team. Later the team will start the activities, starting from an info-point in "Calendimaggio" public events to promote and launch the activity. The team will be also present in other several public events and placed. The action will be developed also in schools, parishes, nursing homes, summer children's camps and in the Municipality offices, etc. In addition, to improve public awareness and behaviour change in waste management, Legambiente will organise social dinners focusing on "waste" in different areas of the city.

The activities held under this umbrella have been split taking into account their specific characteristics:

- SE1.1 Dinner or Lunch with waste. Self-organized dinner, whereby the participants are invited to bring their own food and tableware to share. During this event there are facilitators explaining different aspects of the project, inviting them to use the apps and games, as the Waste2Sort, filling satisfaction surveys, and other aspects. [↗](#)
- SE1.2 Sensitization activity in public spaces or existing activities. A new stand available to promote W4T activities and get in touch with citizens in different events. Different activities were executed in this frame: music, street theatre, questionnaires to check the attitude about separate collection and prevention, samples of bags and containers were delivered, etc. [↗](#)
- SE1.3 Elderly people house activities. Preparatory events with staff, sorting game during social events such as lunches and dinners organized by the old people centre information desk. [↗](#)
- SE1.4 Sensitization in schools. Presentation to the headmaster of the project and the action, preliminary meetings with teachers, school interventions in each classroom in the primary schools, events with sorting games theatre and clean up the world campaign. Specific training meeting for school janitors. Delivery of waste containers in each classroom and in corridors to improve the separation. Site inspections ante and post interventions. [↗](#)

- SE1.5 Sensitization in summer camps with children. A sorting game “where should I throw this” has been done with children and educators. This was done in 2 rounds: at the beginning and in the end of the camp. ↗
- SE1.6 Test of the Apps and Serious Games. In Seveso or in other interesting context the Apps and Serious Games produced in the framework of W4T project have been tested in order to: sensitize different types of stakeholders, and receive feedbacks about the Apps and their practical use. The Apps have been tested in eco-events, schools, university, and during the everyday life. ↗

OBJECTIVES

To improve waste separation

To reduce the amount of residual waste produced

To avoid punishing acts, involving citizens in a positive and productive way

PROMOTER

Legambiente Lombardia and Seveso Municipality

EXECUTER

Internal Partner

KEY MESSAGES

Let's make a better separation together.

Waste separation could be funny

The public institution and community must give the good example

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Residents in household buildings and buildings administrators, schools, parishes, nursing homes, Summer children's camps and in Municipality offices, foreign people

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: training the “door to door” team to develop sensitization activities. 1 team of 2-4 people

1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents

1.3 Other: Team of trained people to work door to door to explain waste separation and management with a tool box (some products developed during the project, such as sorting game and so on).

2. Equipment: A vehicle, work informs to be recognized

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Performance and music

Leaflets. Realization of facilitation actions with questions and answers, questionnaires, games, related to waste management, to assess the knowledge of the people involved in the sensitization action.

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
S1.1	CA		W2S, EDG, VCG, MT.	
S1.2	CA		W2S, EDG, VCG, MT.	
S1.4			W2S, EDG, VCG, MT.	
S1.6	CA		W2S	

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: April 2017

End date: 21/12/2019

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Type: quantitative and qualitative, periodically

Means: evaluation of the number of people interacting during the visits or events, waste collections company data (number of RFID bags), qualitative evaluation about separate collection during sensitization (visual evaluation, average weight of samples in buildings, presence of other containers for recyclable, correct answers during games for children, etc...), number of questionnaire returned completed.

Result indicators to be calculated:

1. Number of reached people by the funny door-to-door team
2. Total number of RFID bags set out by the users
3. Increase of the quality of the separate collection during the sensitization (qualitative every month)
4. Number of questionnaires completed and returned

Others: social acceptance for different targets (especially parishes, schools, etc.).

See annex 2

EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE

Target groups: operators in community places, households' buildings, general citizens

Information provided: number of operators and citizens participating in the action, and improvement in waste prevention and separation.

Channels used: personal contacts, Web page, local press, mailing list

When: periodically during at the action

9.2 Zero waste events and campaigns “Virtuous Households” (SE2) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

The action aims to select a small number of households (10-20), monitoring very strictly and continuously training them to improve their separated collection rate aiming to zero-waste. These households will receive a training and will be part of a prize so that those with the highest recycling rate and lowest production of overall waste will be awarded. The monitoring of the waste production will be done individually by the families themselves with the help of a monitoring kit (i.e. dynamometer, eco-bags, registry), during the trial (one month), in order to verify the range of improvement. Furthermore, a characterization of residual waste will be done by technicians for the selected households.

Also, some weighting (at least) in two times (before and after the action) will be done by technicians for the whole building hosting the selected households, to compare their results with the average of the building.

The training will consist in a demonstration meeting for all the households, giving suggestions to improve the rate and the quality of separated fractions. There could also be used the Sorting Game, to make the activity easier and funnier. Some synergies could be finding with other communication actions, carried out in Seveso (for instance with "Funny door to door sensitization on residual waste" and PAYT system). A dissemination event in the form of a "peer education" will be organized showing to the other citizens how those households changed their behaviours over the time.

The actions forecast to implement this social strategy are the following:

- SE2.1 Citizens involvement. The main aim of this activity consists in the identification of families agreeing to participate in the social action oriented to increase the quality of separate collection through the weighing of waste. Families were recruited by a public tender published on municipal website. Since the deadline for applying was too short, some families have been directly contacted by municipality and by ARS staff. [↗](#)
- SE2.2 Training and monitoring period. Virtuous households families have to periodically weight their waste streams (organic, multi-material, paper, glass, unsorted waste, all waste carried to the municipal ecological platform) and communicate it during the action. Therefore, they received a dynamometer and a periodical visit from the municipal team. An excel sheet was everyday fulfilled and for the participation every family received a reward. [↗](#)
- SE2.3 Feedback activities. Once close the monitoring period, it's necessary to give feedbacks to participating families and spread the results of the action towards all the citizens if possible, with a peer-to-peer event. [↗](#)
- SE2.4 Second stage: Households focusing on waste prevention. Virtuous households families 2.0 have to periodically weight their waste streams (organic, multi-material,

paper, glass, unsorted waste, all waste carried to the municipal ecological platform) and communicate it during the action. ARS was in charge to verify if this activity was carried out by all the family at least one a week. Each family recruited received a dynamometer to weight their waste. ↗

OBJECTIVES

Reduce the amount of waste produced and increase the rate of separated waste in selected households.

Test and verify what types of communication actions could be applied to all the citizens in order to produce a substantial improvement on waste production and collection.

Sensitize the other citizens about the possibilities to change their behaviour in managing their waste, with a low impact in everyday life, and inform about the produced benefits to the all society and to the environment.

PROMOTER

SEVESO, with the coordination of ARS

EXECUTER

Internal-partner

KEY MESSAGES

Waste production could be reduced to almost zero, through some behaviours that can even adopted by citizens at home (e.g. avoiding the purchase of disposable products, optimizing the separate collection of waste, etc.).

Everyone has to do its part to get these goals. Changing our habits is not so difficult, with great benefits for environment and society.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Selected households and citizens from building with different characteristics.

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: The training for households will be done once at the beginning of the action. Trainers must have technical knowledge but also good communication skills, in order to easy speak with different types of people and family. The training will be in tune with the knowledge of the households about the correct waste management (for instance, in some cases it will be more technical, in other one very basic). A large part of the training activity will consist in periodically checking their compliance to the monitoring protocol, giving them suggestions if needed. The aim is to understand whether some basic but well-explained suggestions could be enough to reach high levels of separate collection. Quantity: 1 or 2 trainers

1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents: The employees of the Seveso Municipality, involved in W4T project, will have the role of informers if the selected households need more information or want to solve their doubts about the correct way to manage waste. Furthermore, the employees will have to give the information about the action "Virtuous households towards zero waste" to all the citizens that want to know more about it, in order to sensitize them and generate a virtuous circle. Quantity: 3 or 4 informers

1.3. Other: Waste experts supporting families in order to solve their doubts about separate collection. They will also be responsible to check their own reporting sheets about waste weights and will perform specific measurements of the waste weights/quality.

2. Equipment: The monitoring of the waste produced by the households over the time will be done through specific equipment to weight the waste (i.e. dynamometer, eco-bag, and registry). The need of other materials or equipment could emerge in developing the action.

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

How-to-do rules to be left to households after the first training and Informative page on Municipality web-site. Updated version of "Where do I throw it?" will be prepared after the action and made available to all citizens

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
S2.1				
S2.2	LTA		W2S EDG	
S2.3				
S2.4	LTA		W2S EDG	

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: 01/09/2017 June-August: prepare criteria

September-October: documents and public notice for the competitions
November-December: implement the action
2018 evaluation of the results
Spring 2018: peer education event
End date: Spring 2018
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS
Type: Waste analysis (weigh and quality)
Means: To achieve and verify the improvement in households behaviour it's fundamental to verify periodically (at least two times, one before and one after the action) the weigh and the quality of the waste produced, by each fraction (unsorted and sorted waste). The data will be stored in a specific data-base. Social acceptance of the action will be tested through evaluation of compliance of the contest's rules.
Results indicators to be calculated
1. Number of households and number of people involved
2. Quantity of waste, by type, produced by each household before and after the training period
3. Separate collection rate for each household before and after the action
4. Percentage of recyclable waste in unsorted waste and comparison of the results of the selected households with the average of their building and of the city
Other: Social acceptance of the action See annex 2.
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: Citizens
Information provided: Number of households involved, training carried out, materials provided, improvement in waste production and separate collection rate
Channels used: One dissemination public event in the form of a "peer education" at the end of the action. Information on Municipal website.
When: At the end of the action

9.3 Ecoevents (SE3) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

In the oaks forest area, in Seveso, during the summer, there are a lot of events. The bigger ones have around 3.000 participants for every lunch and dinner. Without the proper planning, huge amounts of catering and lightweight packaging waste are generated during the events.

- SE3.1 Preparation of the criteria, tendering and purchasing needs for the Ecoevents. Seveso, setting up a new regulation, will define criteria for a specific number of events to be organized there or in other places of the city. Seveso Municipality will purchase the

necessary equipment to support these eco-events, specifically aiming at using washable catering, also economically supporting the Associations in order to manage dishwasher, etc. The Associations, implementing Eco-events, will have a reduced waste fee. ↗

- SE3.2 Celebration and monitoring of the Ecoevents. These events will be monitored by calculating indicators (overall waste produced and separated composition of waste, etc.), that are related to the environmental impact, comparing to the other events where no zero waste practices have been implemented. In relation of these events, there will be some activities of sensitization and information of the citizens and associations organizing events in Seveso area. ↗

OBJECTIVES

Reduce the amount of waste produced

Increase the rate of separated waste

Sensitize the citizenship and the associations organizing events about the proper manage of waste, aimed to reduce its production and to better perform the separate collection, and, more in general, about environment impacts of everyday life.

PROMOTER

Seveso, with the coordination of ARS

EXECUTER

Different associations organizing events

KEY MESSAGES

Waste production could be reduced to almost zero, through some behaviours that can even adopted by citizens at home (e.g. avoiding the purchase of disposable products) and by associations (e.g. organizing an Eco-event instead of a not-environmentally friendly one).

Associations organizing events must follow the same Municipal rules about separate collection, as citizens do.

The use of washable catering (dishes, cutlery, and glasses), when used properly, reduces waste and the overall impacts on environment (e.g. responsible use of resources, as energy or water, etc.).

Other: Everyone could do something to get these goals. Changing our habits is not so difficult.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Citizens

Associations implementing eco-events

Association managing the structure

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: To make the Associations able to carry out an Eco-event, the Municipality has to contact them in order to inform about the possibility to carry out an Eco-event in the Municipal area, with a discount on the waste fee by means of a general meeting. Then, Municipality will organize a specific training on how to manage an Eco-event and

how to be compliant with the new regulation about Eco-events. The Municipality has to motivate the most reluctant Associations that perform an Eco-event could be not so difficult. The training will be possibly carried out at the Municipal area for events. Quantity: 1 or 2 trainers for each season

1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents: Before the events, one member of Municipality staff must organize a promotion campaign on the eco-events of the season, the reason behind this new campaign and each Association has to promote its own event. During the events, in order to make citizens aware that they are participating to an Eco-event, one or two members of the association's staff or of Legambiente, when possible, could explain what are the most important features of an Eco-event and how to reduce the produced waste and properly do the separate collection. Quantity: 1 or 2 informers for each eco-event.

1.3. Other: The Waste collection company that is in charge to collect the waste in the Municipality of Seveso has to be aware that there will be some Eco-events needing a specific attention. In fact, at the end of each event, the Waste collection company has to collect the waste, separated by fractions. Technicians will weigh produced waste, in order to monitor the events and, if possible, the associations will be provided by a specific RFID bag for unsorted waste. The Municipality has to well explain these needs and to inform the Waste collection company about the events' season calendar. Quantity: The Association managing the structure will have to engage 1 or 2 people in charge to manage the dishwasher.

2. Equipment: washable catering, dishwasher, waste dispensers, waste separation area, tap water dispenser, furniture, dish soap, etc.

An information point (i.e. gazebo), informative place mats and other communication material

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Leaflets, posters of the events' season calendar (by Municipality). Page on Municipality and/or Associations web-site (if any), roll-up. Informative place mats for each eco-event

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
S3.1				
S3.2			W2S PG	

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: 01/05/2017.

End date: 30/09/2019

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Type: Waste analysis, number of participants

Means: Some main objectives of the Eco-events are: reduction of unsorted waste, organic waste and packaging, increase of separate collection rate. To achieve and verify this goals it's fundamental to measure the performances of each Eco-events related to the number of

<p>participants. The data have to be then processed and stored in a specific data-base. Social acceptance of the action will be tested through specific questionnaires to citizens and organizers during the events.</p>
<p>Results indicators to be calculated</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of Eco-events 2. Number of meals served in Eco-events 3. Rate of selective collection reached in each event (%) 4. Unsorted waste produced during eco-events/number of meals prepared, compared to non eco-events
<p>Other: Global cost for setting up and organizing Eco-events during the project (€) Social acceptance of the action. See annex 2.</p>
<p>EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE</p>
<p>Target groups: Associations and citizens</p>
<p>Information provided: Citizens: number of participants, level of consciousness, level of satisfaction of Eco-events / Associations: number of Associations organizing Eco-event for each season, level of acceptance and engagement.</p>
<p>Channels used: Common municipal channels (telephone, mailing, Facebook, twitter, etc.), specific surveys with citizens participating and associations</p>
<p>When: Citizens: during the Eco-events / Associations: at the of the Eco-events season</p>

9.4 Pay as you throw introduction-communication (SE4) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

Seveso introduced in the beginning of 2015 the use of iBag for residual waste: it's a blue transparent bag, with a RFID tag for automatic monitoring of every delivery. It's delivered to every household, even in multi-family buildings (this is a unique feature of Seveso with respect to others). In the framework of W4T, Seveso wants to change its municipal regulation in order to introduce a PAYT scheme for the municipal waste tax. It is called TARIP in Italy (punctual waste tax). Seveso is already at a very high 75,5% separate collection rate so it doesn't aim at increasing a lot this value, but rather at introducing a fair method.

The implementation of the PAYT system in Seveso will follow the next steps:

- SE4.1 Monitoring of the results with RFID bags, tax calculations and preparation of the campaign. Setting PAYT parameters require to implement the regulation and scheme in Seveso. To do this, data regarding the experimental use of RFID bags were collected to have as much information as possible. [↗](#)
- SE4.2 Implementation campaign. After the approval of the local regulation by the City Council, several actions were done to inform citizens about the new scheme. Public presentations, and letters were sent to each household explaining the new tax, what they are going to pay taking into account the separation habits, how to purchase the personalized bags, etc. The blue bags with RFID started to be counted in order to introduce PAYT in Seveso. [↗](#)
- SE4.3 Incidences resolution and feedback to citizens. These activities regard: littering monitoring and information campaigns, street bins removal, apps for citizens informing in their waste behaviour. They continue over the time with the aim to complement the PAYT action in waste reduction. [↗](#)
- SE4.4 Littering monitoring and dedicated campaign. This action was planned through the use of a littering app developed in Seveso by a local organization to register and share incidences. Unfortunately, it was not possible to use it continuously because of some technical developing problems this organization had.

OBJECTIVES

Introduce a fair method for waste tax rewarding virtuous citizens

Increase the rate of separated waste

Spreader a double message, residual waste can be minimized by both increasing recycling and implementing prevention actions.

PROMOTER

SEVESO, with the coordination of ARS and SOFTLINE

EXECUTER

Internal partner

KEY MESSAGES

<p>PAYT is a method to promote fairness. With the introduction of PAYT, some users (the more virtuous ones) may experience a decrease but some others may also experience an increase.</p> <p>PAYT aims at transparency. In the invoice citizens will get customized information of their production, economic balances and benefits of recycling etc.</p> <p>The introduction of PAYT should be participative; every citizen must be aware of its advantages this change and bad behaviours like littering will be punished.</p>				
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION				
Domestic waste generator and non-domestic waste generator				
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
1. Human resources.				
1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: The introduction of PAYT should be participatory, each citizen should be aware of its advantages. Bad behaviours such as littering will be punished.				
1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents: Many hours will be dedicated by the internal staff of the municipality to train about PAYT when citizens will come to the Ecology Office to get a roll of blue iBag (even if there is an automatic machine, there will be many questions in the beginning). Quantity of 2 educators				
1.3. Other: Legambiente will use part of the time of the "funny door to door sensitization" personnel to stay close to the automatic bag distributor and in public events and places to educate about PAYT and correct recycling				
2. Equipment: A letter will be sent to all citizens together with the first delivery of the tax invoice (still not PAYT, the old waste tax invoice) in May 2017				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Technical tools: The invoicing module (R2)				
Specific web page of the municipality. Leaflets prepared in cooperation with GELSIA, the waste collection company (to be confirmed its participation). Posters and power points in some meetings to be performed with citizens				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
S4.1	CA			
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: 15/12/2016 first draft of the PAYT regulation.				
New ordinance approval in 30 March 2017. On May 2017 send a letter to all citizens and invoice with the fix part. From the 1 st of May 2017 real PAYT implementation (first invoice with the fixed part of the PAYT). Second invoice expected in November 2017, with the variable part of the PAYT.				
End date: 30/09/2019				

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS
Type: Waste data analysis, economic assessment, customer satisfaction,
Means: The Municipality, together with the Waste management company, GELSIA, will provide the data to calculate the quantitative indicators. Social acceptance of the action will be tested through specific questionnaires to citizens during the PAYT implementation.
Results indicators to be calculated
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. N. of HH participating in the system (%) 2. Number of non-domestic users participating (%) 3. % separate collection increase (total and per fraction) 4. Total waste generation decrease 5. Variation of separate collection and total waste generation in specific waste generators sensitized through the other social actions 6. Users asking more information about PAYT and separate collection at the oaks forest (ecology municipal office)
Other: Number of alerts due to failures of the system (e.g. distribution of bags, wrong invoice, etc.), Number of zero-waste users, Littering or waste abandonment (i.e. Number of cleaning actions by Municipality)
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: Domestic and nondomestic generators
Information provided: Complaints/suggestions
Channels used: personal contacts (ecology office), twitter/Facebook, to Legambiente in their informative points, website, public events
When: Daily especially in the beginning, then less contacts

9.5 Promotion campaign of reusable nappies (SE5)

DESCRIPTION

Together with the Municipality of Seveso, Innova21 will implement an information and awareness campaign on reusable nappies for newborns. The campaign will be focused on families with 0-18-month-old children and future parents. Some vouchers (around 30 per year) will be offered by the Municipality, allowing interested families to test. The aim of this trial period is to allow families to test around 3-4 different types of reusable nappies, in order to be able to identify the best one for their needs.

After the test period (approximately 1 month), parents will be asked to complete a customer satisfaction survey and to declare if they will continue using reusable nappies.

The campaign will include the creation and diffusion of information materials and the organization of meetings with the identified target.

To implement this strategy the next actions are foreseen:

- SE5.1 Engagement of local stakeholders. Engagement of some local stakeholders (associations, paediatricians, nurseries) to reach parents with 0-18 months children.
- SE5.2 Campaign and training development. Innova21 and the Municipality of Seveso have informed 0-18 months children's parents about the possibility to try for free along 1 month the reusable nappies kit. The provider La Ninfea, also offered support for the parents and was also responsible for a short training course about the right way to use the reusable nappies.
- SE5.3 Feedback to participants and general citizens. At the end of the project Innova21 and the Municipality of Seveso will inform the participants and citizens about the campaign results. The activity was very useful to have an approach to parents and also talk with them about other sustainable habits among parenting

OBJECTIVES

Reduce the amount of residual waste produced

Reduce the amount of total residual waste produced

Inform citizens about the convenience of using washable nappies

Inform parents and future parents about the opportunity to test the washable nappies kit

PROMOTER

Seveso, together with Innova21

EXECUTER

Agency Innova21

KEY MESSAGES				
Reusable nappies are more convenient than disposable ones, not only in terms of environmental impact but also regarding the economic impact on families.				
Parents interested in reusable nappies will apply for hiring a kit through vouchers offered by the Municipality.				
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION				
Families with 0-18 months-old children and future parents				
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
1. Human resources.				
1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: an external coach/trainer will realize at least one public meeting aiming at explaining how to use the washable nappies kit. (The provider will make the formation)				
1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents				
1.3. Other: A member of Innova21, with extensive experience on the issue, will define the contents of the communication campaign (1 content editor). An external graphic designer will develop the concept and the coordinated theme for all the communication materials of the campaign (leaflet, totems, etc.).				
2. Equipment: Reusable nappies kits (30 kits per year of 6 reusable nappies of each type (3-4 types), washing service for nurseries				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Leaflets (to be distributed to parents at the moment of registering the new baby, in nursery schools, public library, hospitals, municipality, public events).				
Totems to be exposed at the information points (public library, forest of oaks) Fairy tale about reusable nappies. News on local press.				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
S5.1				
S5.2				
S5.3				
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: 09/2017				
09/2017 identify the provider of reusable nappies				
End date: 31/12/2019				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: Quantity (Number of participants), Quality (level of satisfaction).				

Means: After using the washable nappies kit, parents will be asked to complete a customer satisfaction survey and to declare if they will continue using reusable nappies. After a defined time (3 months), the effective use after the trial (i.e. the purchase of the full kit) and the number of reusable nappies will be monitored by direct contact with parents. Moreover each family at the end of the trial will declare the social acceptance of the action through a specific questionnaire.
Results indicators to be calculated
1. Number of children using reusable nappies all day long in nurseries
2. Number of children using reusable nappies at home and accepted by nurseries
3. Number of vouchers requested
4. Estimated waste avoided by families involved in the action (estimated from the below)
5. % of households saying they are going to use the reusable nappies for their children immediately after the trial
6. number of households saying they are going to use the reusable nappies for their children immediately after the trial
7. % of children effectively using reusable nappies three months after the trial (% on voucher requested)
Other: Social acceptance of the action. See annex 2.
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUPS OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: Parents of 0-18 months-old children, future parents, citizens, general public
Information provided: Number of families participating in the test, level of satisfaction, % of Declarations of future use of washable nappies.
Channels used: web page, Facebook, news on local press
When: periodically during the action

9.6 Reusable nappies campaign for nursery school (SE6) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION

Related to the previous strategy, the pilot will involve also a nursery school, where a washing service will be tested (internally and /or externally). This service will be used for washing nappies used in the kinder garden and also for the ones used at home and delivered at the school by parents.

To implement this strategy the next actions are foreseen:

- SE6.1 Stakeholders engagement (nursery + washing service). 9 nurseries, laundries, and parents were invited in different stages to this initiative in the aim to design and implement the use of reusable nappies. The idea was to try reusable nappies in nurseries, with an internal or external washing service, during 3 months. This activity has had a low convening power. However, the feedback of each stakeholder has been collected as lessons learned in SE6.1 Engagement [↗](#), and SE6.2 Implementation [↗](#).
- SE6.3 Feedback to participants. Due to the low interest this action was not developed.

OBJECTIVES

Reduce the amount of residual waste produced

Reduce the amount of total residual waste produced

Inform parents and future parents about the opportunity to test the washable nappies kit

PROMOTER

Seveso, together with Innova21

EXECUTER

Agency Innova21

KEY MESSAGES

Reusable nappies are more convenient than disposable ones, not only in terms of environmental impact but also regarding the economic impact on families.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Nursery workers and families with 0-18 months-old children and future parents

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: an external coach/trainer will realize at least one training to nursery workers

1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents

1.3. Other: A member of Innova21, with extensive experience on the issue, will

define the contents of the communication campaign				
2 Equipment: Reusable nappies kits, washing service for nurseries				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Leaflets				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
SE6.1	CA			
SE6.2				
SE6.3				
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: 2017				
End date: 31/12/2019				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: Quantity (Number of participants), Quality (level of satisfaction).				
Means: satisfaction survey				
Results indicators to be calculated				
1. Number of children using reusable nappies all day long in nurseries				
2. Number of children using reusable nappies at home and accepted by nurseries				
3. Estimated waste avoided by families involved in the action (estimated from the below)				
4. number of households saying they are going to use the reusable nappies for their children immediately after the trial				
5. % of children effectively using reusable nappies three months after the trial (% on voucher requested)				
Other: Social acceptance of the action. See annex 2.				
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUPS OR GENERAL AUDIENCE				
Target groups: Parents of 0-18 months-old children, future parents, citizens, general public				
Information provided: Number of families participating in the test, level of satisfaction, % of declarations of future use of washable nappies.				
Channels used: web page, Facebook, news on local press				
When: periodically during the action				

			2016												2017												2018												2019											
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
			Use case analysis					Preparatory Actions							Deployment & Integration						Preliminary Test			Full Test																										
			M1					M2							M3						M4			M5																										
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42						
Saves Pilot		Start month																																																
SE1 Citizens Sensitization. Funny door to door		April 2017																																																
SE2 Zero waste events and campaigns "virtuous households"		April 2018																																																
SE3 Ecoevents		may-17																																																
SE4 PAYT		may-17																																																
SE5 Promotion campaign of reusable nappies		Jan 18																																																
SE6 Reusable nappies campaign in a nursery school		Jan 18																																																

Modifications:

SE2: Delayed until March-April 2018

SE5: Preparatory activities in Sep '17, main activities will start in January '18

SE6: Delayed until June 18

Fig. 8 FORECAST: Seveso Social Actions Calendar

10 Environmental Education Program in Cascais

10.1 ID/PAYT containers system (C1)

DESCRIPTION

Communication action to bring awareness to the project to the residents and bin user of the test pilot area, as well as nearby residents or waste enthusiasts that voluntarily want to participate. Involving citizens in the implementation of a new system through participatory models using awareness social actions and users as potential information share points.

In a first stage, the bins will not be blocked as users will need to get used to the new method of card reading and waste selection. The action will be multi stage as it will involve families with the use of printed materials, workshops and personal support.

- C1.1 Preparation activities. Inquiries, pre and post deploy, to the local population living or using the test area for the W4T project are crucial to fully understand constrains and views mentioned on the waste collection system. It will also provide information regarding system changes through regular contact with people by retrieving their feedback and likeness. We are considering a sample of 500 people
- C1.2 Implementation campaign – condominium meetings. Meetings with administration of each condominium in the target area for engagement of key-citizens using all potential from their local knowledge and gathering capabilities. This was not a successful action as the residents were not interested in attending
- C1.3 Implementation campaign - workshops and Door to Door visits. Workshops about waste management and family resource efficiency. Engage with citizens with proximity and direct contact
- C1.4 Gamification Award System. Reward the users who have demonstrated good environmental behaviours with awards from municipality. This will be achieved by an award system implemented within the apps to be developed.
- C1.5 Promotion of the W4T Apps and games. Presentation and promotion of the Apps and games by the trainers/educators within the different actions (meeting, workshops, etc.) and via the social media and web.
- C1.6 Feedback to citizens. This action aims to create interactive ways to share the information on the ways in which they directly helped to achieve a more sustainable environment. An annual meeting is organized to achieve this objective.

OBJECTIVES

Present the project to all individual potential users in the target area

Involving citizens in the implementation of a new system through participatory models using mobile applications and awareness social actions

Increase recycling and environmentally responsible behaviour of citizens

Engage citizens in gamification activities as well as with the Waste4Think Project

PROMOTER

Cascais - EMAC

EXECUTER
Cascais - EMAC /Internal-partner
KEY MESSAGES
Increase recycling and environmentally responsible behaviour of citizens with the new collecting PAYT system.
The introduction of PAYT should be participative; every citizen must be aware of its advantages. Each citizen can make a difference and household environmental performance can also help financial efficiency. Bad behaviours like littering will be punished.
Waste management can be fun and useful for households and citizens of all ages
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION
Residents of the target area in one neighbourhood, 2432 inhabitants, 1093 families living in 1505 apartments.
Administration of each condominium
Nearby users and parish inhabitants
General public
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION
1. Human resources.
Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents: contact and train the Administration of each condominium in order to later be able to inform the residents (also provide info about the citizen app-award system)
Educators and informers. Tasks and contents: environmental awareness team will locally, publicly and individually present the project to mentioned target audience by means of door-to-door visits, public events, resident's workshops, communication materials delivery, etc. The staff will also promote the use of App and Games.
These workshops will evolve in a performance assessment for users with related activities and games between them. This will include the sorting game and other apps.
1.3. Other: Specific Communication staff to develop the inquiries, Platform manager: Content management (Facebook)
2. Equipment: information support near bins, poster in bin and delivery points and stickers, all with online references. Identification system for the bins and users
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS
IT tools free web app for surveys, Facebook group
Promotional video (promotes and describes the project in a clear and objective way so that it can be perceived by all citizens.)
Booklets/leaflet: Communication support materials to achieve other communication platforms for all potential users and residents
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
C1.1				
C1.2				
C1.3			EDG	
C1.4	FA CA		W2S VCG MT	
C1.5	CA	DE6		
C1.6	CA		W2S VCG MT	

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: after September

Activity 1: before September; Activity 2/3/4: Nov 2017, Activity 5/6 Nov 2017

End date: end of the project.

Activity 1: to be held every 3/5 months or depending significant system changes

Activity 2/3/4/5: end of the project

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Type: waste analysis, user analysis and participation counter, inquiries post-deploy, assistance list for meeting/workshops, social media follow up

Means: actions/collection service direct monitoring, surveys, tools usage automatic indicators

To achieve and verify the improvement in households behaviour it's fundamental to verify periodically the weigh and the quality of the waste produced, by each fraction (unsorted and sorted waste). The data could be stored in the Municipal data-base.

The participation counter will be necessary to know the participation and level of satisfaction. Inquiries post-deploy will provide complementary info about habits change and service satisfaction

Results indicators to be calculated

Number of households participating (Acceptance/ participation within target area, number HH with ID system)

Number of users actually participating (%) (number HH using the ID to access de bins)

Number of alerts due to incorrect use of the bins

Number of usages of the ID system per fraction (TOTAL AVERAGE PER MONTH)

% of separate collection (it is also Tech KPI)

Number of claims of benefits (also per type of benefit)

Cost of the separate collection

Satisfaction/Acceptance of the new ID system by HH –S.4- (via survey)

Other: number of inquiries, number of meetings/workshops and participants, social media indicators (number of posts, likes, hash tag mentioned, group members), number of video views/shares, number of web views, number of leaflets and booklets delivered. *General Eco-solution indicators (for apps/games)*

See annex 2.
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: Potential users
Information provided: booklet information about the project, benefits and general goals for the users and the local environment. User satisfaction resulting from the inquiries and waste collection results and participation.
Channels used: personal reach by communication staff (personal support, directly to individuals or resident association), poster and leaflets, mailing, media (traditional and online), waste invoices
When: continuously by staff, every 3 months by the invoices, periodically by local media (online/social media and newspapers), every month by the website.

10.2 Tourist engagement (C2) [↗](#)

DESCRIPTION
As tourists have different communication channels and other interests within their stay in the target area, we must also deliver dedicated information in English. Not only to them but to landlords who are relevant tools of dissemination The next actions are foreseen: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C2.1 Information to landlords. This action aims to create interactive ways to inform families and other participants of the PAYT and other W4T initiatives sharing experiences and motivating tourists to reduce waste, and properly separate it. The participation from tourist landlords was very poor although 6 full time monitors were destined to make contact with them. ↗ • C2.2 Dedicated campaign. This action aims to create interactive ways to engage citizens as new participants and beneficiaries. Sharing experiences and motivating tourists to reduce waste, and properly separate it. It also aims to increase awareness to ecological issues and ways in which they can help. ↗
OBJECTIVES
To promote the PAYT system and recycling for short stay citizens (tourists and visitors)
Involve a larger scope of users that could also disseminate the project at their homeland
Further study the reaction of citizens of different nationalities
PROMOTER
Cascais - EMAC
EXECUTER
Cascais - EMAC
KEY MESSAGES
As a tourist, citizens must comply with local rulings and engage with environmental values

The PAYT system is easy to use even as a tourist				
Local communities (namely landlords) have an environmental responsibility				
TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION				
Tourists and landlords from the area				
Occasional beach users				
TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
1. Human resources.				
1.1. Trainers or coaches. staff will organize leaflet delivery through registration from landlords (with the collaboration of condominium managers) and, if necessary, will provide personal support or clarification.				
Educators and informers: staff will organize information and leaflet delivery in touristic areas (beach, restaurants zones, etc.)				
2. Equipment: information support near bins, poster in bin and delivery points and stickers, all with online references. Identification system for the bins and users. Specific and controlled point to deliver the waste in case of no access to the bins or any problem				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Facebook group				
2000 leaflets				
W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
C2.1	CA			
C2.2	CA			
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: spring 2018				
End date: end of the project. After pilot, lock system collective				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: waste analysis, user analysis and participation counter with references to tourist housing				
Means: actions/collection service direct monitoring, surveys, tools usage automatic indicators				
The analysis will be assessed with references to summer months waste production and data crossing with tourist user or housing rentals. The data could be stored in the Municipal database.				
The participation counter with tourist references is necessary to know the participation and level of satisfaction				
Results indicators to be calculated				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of touristic households participating (touristic accommodation houses/apartments registered to use the bins) 				

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of touristic users actually participating (%) (number touristic HH using the ID to access de bins) • Number of touristic HH usages of the ID system per fraction (TOTAL AVERAGE PER MONTH) (via touristic HH ID codes) • % of separate collection (in case there are bins with a majority of touristic HH assigned) • Number of alerts due to incorrect use of the bins (via touristic HH ID codes) • Number of claims of benefits by tourists/landlord (also per type of benefit)
Satisfaction/Acceptance of the new ID system by touristic HH –S.4-(via survey)
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE
Target groups: tourists, visitors and landlords
Information provided: flyer information about the project, benefits and general goals for the local environment and how tourists can contribute with sustainable behaviours. Waste collection results and participation.
Channels used: personal reach by communication staff (personal support, directly to individuals or resident association), leaflets, mailing, Facebook, webpage.
When: after every summer (September)

10.3Waste 4 Think Schools (C3)

DESCRIPTION
<p>Communication program dedicated to both students and schools. The program is designed to interact in classes of different ages and to bring those activities within the family discussion. The involved schools are those within the pilot area or where most students are attending.</p> <p>It will also be a communication platform for the program and IT tools. In a first stage we will promote waste management and recycling with the support of the Games and Learning materials but also with the printed materials. In a later stage we will develop more activities to promote the platform use.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C3.1 Learning materials (mobile games and STEAM lessons) The idea is to integrate and promote W4T in every educational activity of another ongoing project called PESA which has direct contact and a schedule of environmental lessons already coordinated. This action aims to actively engage young citizens and children in educating and raising awareness for environmental issues and how Waste4Think can help them build a more sustainable future. • C3. 3 EMAC own activities. This action aims to actively engage young citizens and children in educating and raising awareness for environmental issues such as climate

change, pollution, waste, circular economy, animal welfare, ecological footprint, healthy and sustainable eating, biodiversity conservation, etc. [↗](#)

OBJECTIVES

Promote PAYT system, the project and waste recycling within the students and school community

Qualify the teaching staff with waste management contents and IT tools (Games and Learning materials).

Provide comprehensive materials and contents for young students of different ages and promote a family discussion with the families.

PROMOTER

Cascais

EXECUTER

Internal-partner

KEY MESSAGES

Children and schools are a key element to promote environmental awareness Systems

Families and general users should participate in the PAYT WASTE4THINK Project

The introduction of PAYT should be participative; every citizen must be aware of its advantages this change and bad behaviours like littering will be punished

Waste management can be fun and useful for households and citizens of all ages

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

Schools within and close to the test pilot area, their students, teachers and staff. Schooling community

Sport clubs or associations (collective social institutions)

General public (youngsters)

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION

1. Human resources.

1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents

1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents: Develop a yearlong communication and educational plan dedicated to schools starting in the middle of the last period of 2016/2017 and a full academic year of 2017/2018.

These activities addressed to students and teachers will simultaneously inform them about the PAYT Systems and help them to spread the word within the families. Each activity will consist of teaching contents in an interactive methodology with short duration using Games and Learning materials as well as other waste management teaching contents from EMAC

Once a week each school will have a presentation, being directly involved in the promotion of environmental awareness tools/programs

1 educator full time during one year.

1.3 Other

2. Equipment: APPs, educational programs from EMAC on waste contents, printed materials from the consortium, online references.

COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

Waste management teaching contents from EMAC awareness department. Other online references.

Posters for school boundaries, printed material from the consortium.

500 environmental awareness items, 500 booklets and publicity structure 6 units in social media and local newspapers

W4T ICT TOOLS APPLIED

See more details in Annex 0

STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
C3.1		DP3 MG1 MG2		
C3.2			W2S EDG VC MT	
C3.3	FA CA	DP3 DP5	EDG	

CALENDAR OF THE ACTION

Start date: 1/03/2017

End date: end of project

MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS

Type: waste analysis, schools collection service follow up, list student and teaching participation in activities. surveys post-deploy (Satisfaction, knowledge learned and info transferred to the families)

Means: actions/collection service direct monitoring, surveys, tools usage automatic indicators

Results indicators to be calculated

Number of schools W4T (number of schools participating)

Number of participating students

Separate collection at schools (%)

Average kg/day per student

Number of students participating in the proposed activities (use of APPs, Games...)

Number of teachers or staff participating in the awareness activities

Satisfaction/Acceptance of the new ID system by HH with children at school –S.4-(via survey)

Satisfaction/Acceptance of the new ID system by schools –S.4-(via survey)

Other: Number of posters displayed. Number of EMAC own activities. General Eco-solution indicators (for apps/games/Learning materials)

EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE

Target groups: students, users and school/association staff

Information provided: booklet information about the project, benefits and general goals for the

users and the local environment. User satisfaction resulting from the surveys and recycling results and participation.

Channels used: personal reach by education staff and teachers, social network and school's communication channels.

When: Games/Learning materials usages-weekly. Survey results after each survey. Feedback about the waste collection model results according to the protocols of the C1

		2016																																									
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12																														
		Use case analysis										M1																															
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7																																			
Cascais Pilot																																											
C1 ID/PAYT containers system	nov-17																																										
C2 W4T Schools	sep-17																																										
C3 Tourist engagement	Spring 18																																										
		2017												2018												2019																	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12						
		Preparatory Actions												M2	Deployment & Integration						M3	Preliminary Test			M4	Full Test						M5											
		8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42							
Cascais Pilot																																											
C1 ID/PAYT containers system	nov-17																																										
C2 W4T Schools	sep-17																																										
C3 Tourist engagement	Spring 18																																										

Fig. 9 FORECAST: Cascais Social Action Calendar

11 Other Integrative Social Actions

11.1 Other Integrative Social Actions

DESCRIPTION

During the project, new opportunities appeared and two actions were organized in order to promote the use of the Virtual Cities as a Serious Game. Unlike the others these implementations have an integrative character, since more than one pilot and partner participated.

- Z9.5 LAN PARTY. The Euskal Encounter is a multitudinous meeting of computer enthusiasts and professionals who seek to exchange knowledge and carry out all kinds of computer-related activities over several days. In this case the W4T game Virtual Cities, was used to make a competition with prizes. [↗](#)
- Virtual Cities International Competition. It is a competition between students from the NTUA and UPatras universities in Greece and DEUSTO in Spain. This tournament was organized to promote use of the Virtual City Game [↗](#)

OBJECTIVES

Promotion of the project and the game among universities and citizens

Test the games for training and raising awareness about circularity to raise awareness.

Improve the knowledge of key concept related to waste hierarchy, mobility, cradle to cradle design, water management, energy efficiency and other systems as part the process of building a circular economy.

PROMOTER

The Consortium

EXECUTER

Internal partners

KEY MESSAGES

Be a decision maker, drive the Circular Economy agenda forward to unlock economic, environmental and social benefits for your community and region.

With this serious game you become a high technical decision-maker in order to raise the circularity of your town.

At the same time, you can see how other cities are also trying to be more circular.

Interacting with other cities you have the opportunity to make common choices in order to improve your circularity!

Involving gamers creates new spaces of creativity and helps obtain new ideas by students.

TARGET GROUP DESCRIPTION

University student with a strong emphasis on the student of the University of Deusto, Upatras and NTUA

TOOLS AND MEANS NEEDED TO IMPLEMENT THE ACTION				
1. Human resources.				
1.1. Trainers or coaches. Tasks and contents				
1.2. Educators and informers. Tasks and contents				
2. Equipment: Prizes for the winners of the competitions, materials needed to organize the game competition				
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
Prizes for the winners of the competitions, materials needed to organize the game competition				
Web campaign				
See more details in Annex 0				
STRATEGY CODE	APPS	LEARNING MATERIALS	SERIOUS GAMES	OTHER
Z8.1			VCG	
CALENDAR OF THE ACTION				
Start date: 8 th November 2019				
End date: 23 th November 2019				
MONITORING STRATEGY AND EXPECTED RESULTS				
Type: Metrics				
Means: Direct measurements				
Results indicators to be calculated				
1. Number of participants				
2. Satisfaction				
EXPECTED FEEDBACK OF THE RESULTS TO THE TARGET GROUP OR GENERAL AUDIENCE				
Target groups: Participants on the competition				
Information provided: Publication of the results of the competitions				
Channels used: Conference in each university				
When: Once				

12 Expected results

One of the expected results of the environmental education strategies is to change the behaviour of the different target groups (citizens, students, retailers) toward a high level of awareness and empowerment to change in consumption and waste management habits, and also promoting the prevention of waste and using the produced waste as a resource in a sustainable manner, reducing negative environmental impacts in cities.

Moreover, with the implementation of the campaigns of each Pilot explained, Waste4Think want to quantify and qualify the behavioural changes.

13 Follow up methodology

Monitoring the effectiveness of the social actions is a must in order to accumulate a better knowledge in this field. For this reason, a specific methodology for both qualitative and quantitative evaluation has been described and will be improved during the project. The final objective is to achieve knowledge of the efficiency of every social action so we can describe with detail the lessons learnt, and continuously improve, emend mistakes and replicate the successful actions.

13.1 Quantitative reporting

As well as for the technical baseline, the results and impact of the social actions (IT and non-IT) developed in each pilot are going to be reported.

Some of the impacts are cross-cutting and will be described following the general technical protocols. Generation per capita, separate collection rate, etc. are a result both from technical development of the W4T collections and social actions (Fig. 1010).

Nevertheless, there are also other impacts that are needed to be calculated and reported.

These are the "social impacts" agreed in some dynamic sessions among the pilots to be calculated as KPI: behavioural changes in terms of consumption, prevention or awareness among the different target groups. Another group of indicators to be calculated are those regarding the satisfaction about the different actions.

Fig. 10 Social Actions Monitoring

Although each pilot carries out different actions, there will be a part of compulsory general monitoring with common indicators for all the pilots and actions. On this section each Pilot has to report the general Social KPI as they are described in the D1.1:

- Number of collection points accessible to disability people.
- Green jobs created
- Legislative changes proposed
- Social acceptance

However, specific quantitative monitoring for each action is needed and described in the Excel annex of this report.

Especially for indicators about habits change in terms of prevention and consumption and separate collection, a general comparison is needed in order to quantify the changes produced by Waste4think as a whole. In this sense, a baseline before starting with the activities of the project about knowledge and habits is needed and, at least, other final survey about it will be done at the end of the project. This macro indicator will be then “spread” and complemented with partial results calculated for each action.

In the Monitoring Excel some advises and suggestions are given in order to help the pilots to fulfil these requirements. It’s needed to send the Monitoring Excel each time new data is added, so, at the beginning of the project (general baseline) and each time an action /group of actions is developed.

In any case, in chapter 13.4, the coordination methodology to ensure the fulfilment of all the requested information is explained.

13.2 Qualitative reporting

The quantitative monitoring will be the key success factor of this social action plan in terms of cost-benefit evaluation of the environmental education activities that are not usually monitored. The results of this monitoring will be of high interest in order to have a better knowledge on how to improve waste prevention and separate collection by changing habits, increasing awareness and increasing empowerment among the different target groups.

Nevertheless, qualitative reporting is also of high relevance, in order to assure the reporting of the lessons learnt, both in terms of detection of success factors and also errors to be avoided.

For qualitative reporting the following factsheet should be provided by the pilots. The best practices developed during the project will be used for the “Best Practices Book” at the end of Waste4Think process.

NAME OF THE ACTION:
STRATEGIC LINE RELATED:
Location:
Success of the action (0-5):
Waste streams:
Waste management stages:
Period of the implementation:
Short description:
Current status (finished, onwards.)
Communication tools (main media used etc.)
Training tools
Other tools developed during the campaign (financial, local, ordinance...)
Target group and N. of stakeholders involved (expected and effective)
Rate of participation (% or number)
Key points of success
Description of the monitoring methodology, if any (surveys, waste weighting, ...).
Qualitative environmental, social and economic impact / benefit
Costs detailed? If yes, details, possibly also normalized (per citizen, per ton...)
Add some pictures of the activity
Links to press releases, etc.
Lessons learnt
Other interesting information
Key words

Fig. 11 *Factsheet of the qualitative reporting*

Each time a social action is developed is needed to send this factsheet fulfilled with the maximum information and description of the activity. As some of the actions are recurrent or so similar or are of “less importance” in the framework of the environmental education strategy, in some cases it would be accepted to fulfil one factsheet for all the similar actions.

This will be agreed between BCN, as social Actions Plan coordinators, and the PILOTS leaders.

Again, to assure the coordination of contents with WP7, a protocol has been developed with ACLIMA and LEGAMBIENTE, as it is explained in chapter 11 and in D7.1.

13.3 Specific monitoring for Zamudio's action

The general objective of social actions is to promote a change of thinking and behaviour in people towards the society of sustainability. Social actions in the framework of an environmental education strategy are necessary for a real and smoother achievement of this change of habits. The final objective is to develop critical thinking among different target groups, which it means to promote an objective analysis of facts to form a judgment and decide an action. Critical thinking is self-directed, self-disciplined, self-monitored, and self-corrective thinking.

To ensure the effectiveness and the integration of these actions and to try to quantify this change of thinking and behaviour in people towards the society of sustainability, we are going to develop a whole monitoring of the packaging prevention campaign developed in Zamudio in the framework of the Waste4Think.

The objective of this deeper analysis is to quantify the impacts caused by these social actions, mainly applying a Life Cycle Thinking methodology. To do that, a review of the existing studies has been done to try to develop a new methodology to monitor and evaluate the impacts of the social actions from the environmental, social and economic point of view:

- 1) Environmental: the change that we request has a direct effect on the consumption; it is about changing the lifestyle especially focusing onto the prevention and the selective collection to make effective the circular economy.
- 2) Social: the actions are aimed to the society as a whole, either it is though a general way or determined by target groups. We have to watch and recognize which other factors can have influence: gender equality, accessibility.
- 3) Economic: those social actions and the resulting change of habits have an economic impact, and that is what we want to calculate through figuring out the cost-benefit of the social actions performed.

13.3.1 The Social foot Print

Social actions are not easy to relate with environmental, economic and social impacts. The data is not widely available and are resource-intensive to collect. For these reasons, studies on the social performance of products and services are much less widely available. As part of the research made by the Waste4Think project, an alternative methodology called social footprint, developed by Weidema (2018) has been identify and recognized as the best methodology to analyse this kind of actions performance. The Social Footprint can be defined as “the equity-weighted share of the wellbeing and productivity gap that can be ascribed to a specific product, a specific production or consumption activity, or the consumption within a specific geographical area”. Some of its multiple features are that:

- Provides a complete measure of all social, biophysical and economic externalities
- This is ensured by the top-down approach taking its starting point in the determination of the global wellbeing and productivity gap.

- As it applies a uniform monetary valuation, the method has a focus on poverty and also allows comparisons and trade-offs between different decision options.
- Is faster because it has low data requirement, while it fully allows the integration of more extensive data sources for further detailing.
- Its scalable, so that the same methodology can be applied for decision making on individual products, specific production and consumption activities, and geographical areas, and be additive across these.

Fig. 12 The concept of social footprint (SF)

Production and consumption generate both detrimental and beneficial effects on human wellbeing (utility): beneficial effects are captured by income redistribution, and detrimental effects are captured by the productivity impact (Muñoz et al. 2018).

The method is conceptually illustrated in Fig. 12. The social footprint is calculated as the difference between two indicators:

- Income redistribution (IR): the utility-weighted, purchase-power corrected life cycle costs. This indicator evaluates the transfer of income between societal groups. Transfers between affluent and impoverished groups are valued favourably, and vice versa.
- Productivity impact (PI): the utility-weighted, purchase-power corrected well-being and productivity gap. This gap is the difference between the potential productivity of a given economic activity in the absence of externalities and its actual productivity. It can be understood as the overall value of externalities associated to a production. Typically, the PI is of higher magnitude than the IR and it is essentially country-specific rather than technology-specific.

The social footprint is an innovative method. Practical studies have been performed in several industrial sectors, such as food (Schenker and Weidema 2017), textiles (Weidema 2018), waste management (Muñoz et al. 2018) and construction (Muñoz 2019).

13.3.2 The waste prevention campaign in Zamudio [↗](#)

Zamudio is a municipality with around 3,200 inhabitants living in 1.259 dwellings. The campaign lasted from September 2018 to February 2019, and during this time the municipality offered its citizens 460 kits of reusable bags and containers that could be picked up, for free, from the town hall. The kits were composed by:

- 4 bags for the fruit shop
- 1 fishmonger's container (blue)
- 1 butcher's shop (red)
- 1 isothermal bag for fishmongers and butchers
- 1 reusable sandwich wrap

Fig. 13 *The reusable packaging materials distributed in the Zamudio campaign: reusable containers for meat and fish, bitsybags for fruit and vegetables, Bocn'Roll, Isothermal bag.*

The main aim of this campaign was to reduce the number of single-use food wrappers and plastic bags used by the citizens while shopping in groceries, butcheries and fishmongers.

To achieve the reduction and encourage the use of reusable kits, the municipality used a gamification dynamic to distribute them. The kits were available in two stages. First, citizens were invited to collect the 4 reusable bags and 2 rigid plastic containers from the council hall. After that, and thanks to the use of these items, each neighbour received from the associated trade, cumulative labels that were needed to obtain the second part of the reusable items (isothermal bag and reusable sandwich wrapper).

The research project collected data on the level of penetration of these reusable packaging materials in local shopping. 334 citizens, 26.52% of the dwellings, participated in a baseline inquiry dedicated to know the consumption habits of the population. In the final stage of the campaign, 10% of the

citizens who were part of it, carried out another survey with the aim of finding out about using habits of the reusable packaging in the long term, even if it was not exactly that provided by the project.

13.3.3 Background system, and modelling approached in Zamudio

The aim of this study was to determine whether or not the implemented strategies during the Zamudio campaign, related to reduction of packaging waste by local shoppers, involve a lower social footprint, when compared to the former situation. Therefore, the functional unit is the provision of packaging materials for shopping in groceries, butcheries and fishmongers in Zamudio during one year.

The life cycle model was built using the EXIOBASE (Wood et al. 2015) v.3 as background database. EXIOBASE is a global multi-regional input-output database based on the national and international statistical accounting of trade between industries and between countries. This ensures a complete coverage of the global economy and thus overcomes some of the problems of cut-offs and incompleteness often found in traditional LCA databases. The database links together 43 countries and 5 rest-of-world regions by international trade. In terms of elementary flows, it includes 33 mineral and non-renewable resources, land occupation, 49 emissions to air, 3 emissions to water, and 9 emissions to soil. The most recent year for which primary data are available in the database is year 2011.

The database has been implemented by 2.0 LCA consultants in its version 3.3.16 in the LCA software SimaPro and extended with social footprint indicators: each producing industry in EXIOBASE was assigned a share of the national wellbeing and productivity gap and utility-weighted. The same was done with the value added, in order to obtain each industry's income redistribution effect.

Two practical aspects on how we used EXIOBASE in the study are the following:

- As mentioned above, activities expressed in monetary units use Euro with their value in 2011 as reference flow. In order to use these activities, we express inventory activities as Euro with their value in 2019 (or the corresponding year) and then apply an inflation correction, of 0.925 €2011/€2019, obtained from Eurostat (2019). In the presentation of results, however, we scale up all costs again to their value in 2019.
- The EXIOBASE datasets chosen to represent all activities in the study are classified in the SimaPro software with the label 'Product markets, hybrid units. These data sets represent consumption mixes for the particular sector and country of interest. As an example, the product market for plastic and rubber products in Spain reflects the consumption mix of these products in Spain, which are not necessarily produced in this country. The origin of the plastic products is determined in the database by means of the underlying trade statistics, which include imports and exports. Also, these data sets include not only the production of the goods/services of interest, but also their distribution (transport and retail), according to *average* figures for each economic sector. For this reason, in the inventory analysis we do not address *specific* transports for background activities.

An ISO 14044-compliant (ISO 2006) consequential life cycle inventory (LCI) modelling approach was used in this study. This means that included suppliers of products and services are those most likely to be affected, while allocation is avoided by substitution. Since this study does not focus on environmental impacts, a parallel LCI assessment was done and is attached.

13.3.4 Product system, scope, boundaries and Foreground

The results of this study are intended to inform the Waste4Think consortium and the European Commission about the potential social performance of implemented strategies. Therefore, capital goods and infrastructure were included in the foreground and background system. No cut-offs have been applied, so that all affected activities that could be identified were included in the study.

Two scenarios were assessed:

- **Business as usual (BAU):** in this scenario, we consider the consumption of (typically single-use) packaging used in a ‘no-campaign’ situation.

The study tracked the entire supply chain for provision of packaging materials to local shoppers in Zamudio. In the BAU scenario, the affected types of packaging were carrier bags, expanded polystyrene (EPS) trays, polyethylene (PE)-coated paper, wax paper and ultralight plastic bags. These are the materials identified as being typically used in local shops to wrap food in groceries, butcheries and fishmongers. The social footprint considered the full life cycle of these materials, namely the production, use, and disposal. The use phase, however, does not involve any impacts from the point of view of the social footprint.

Fig. 14 Life cycle diagram for the ‘BAU’ scenario.

- **Campaign:** in this scenario, we considered the consumption of reusable packaging according to the results of the Zamudio campaign. In this scenario, shoppers use reusable containers during their shopping, however this does not completely avoid the use of single-use packaging, which is also considered. On top of the activities considered for the BAU scenario, this one includes the production of the plastic reusable containers and bitsybags, their use for a certain period of time and their final disposal when they are no longer usable. In this scenario the use phase involves the activity of washing the reusable containers with a certain frequency. The figures we used reflect an extrapolation of the improvement rate reached by 10% of the citizens who participated in the campaign. In other words, the ‘Campaign’

Fig. 15 Life cycle diagram for the 'Campaign' scenario.

As part of the social footprint study, we calculated the life cycle costs of the two scenarios. When the Campaign scenario leads to a different life cycle cost than the BAU scenario, this leads to a monetary imbalance that is addressed in the study as what is called a rebound effect (Consequential LCA 2015). When an activity leads to a reduction or increase in costs compared with a reference, this means the corresponding affected economic actor/s are left with either additional or less disposable income. This income is assumed to be spent in other activities, which in turn have an environmental impact and social footprint. The social footprint of this expenditure was calculated in the study on a per € basis, assuming the average expenditure behaviour in Spain according to EXIOBASE.

13.3.5 Foreground system

Consumption of packaging materials

Consumption of packaging materials by the citizens of Zamudio during one year has been provided by BCN Ecología, based on the surveys carried out during the campaign, and extrapolated to the entire municipality. The table below summarizes the amount of packaging estimated on an annual basis. For reusable packaging, namely bitsybags and containers, the annual consumption accounts for the expected useful life of these materials, which was estimated in 5 years in both cases by BCN Ecología. The list³ includes several packaging materials combining paper and plastic, namely wax paper and plastic-covered paper. In these cases, it was assumed that 80% of the mass corresponds to paper and 20% to either plastic or wax.

³ ANNEX analysis of Zamudio surveys

Table 1. Consumption of packaging materials in the two scenarios.

Packaging material	BAU	Campaign
Carrier bags, kg	1,021	361
PE-covered EPS trays, kg	251	100
PE-coated paper, kg	655	280
Wax paper, kg	127	50
Ultralight plastic bags, kg	219	17
Compostable bag, kg	0.4	0.08
Bitsybag, kg	0	3.7
Reusable container, kg	0	22
Total consumption, plastics, kg	1,623	560
Total consumption, wax, kg	25	10
Total consumption, paper, kg	625	264

Disposal of packaging materials

Disposal of packaging materials used in Zamudio was included taking into account the actual recycling rates at the municipality, as communicated by BCN Ecología. The latter supplied the waste production and collection rates in the municipality for the target waste fractions (paper and plastic packaging), excluding the contributions from the local industrial state, as this would otherwise distort the statistics for domestic waste management. The packaging paper recycling rate was 11%, while the plastic film recycling rate was 37%. For materials not sent for recycling, a disposal mix consisting of 66% incineration and 34% land filling was established, representing the average disposal mix in Bizkaia, obtained from its waste management plan (Diputación Foral de Bizkaia 2005).

The activity of waste collection in EXIOBASE is quantified in monetary units. The cost of mixed waste collection has been quantified at 59 €2014/ton, while the cost of packaging waste collection has been quantified at 238 €2014/ton (Fullana et al. 2017), in both cases representing typical costs in Spain. The activity of waste sorting for separately collected waste, also quantified in monetary units, was obtained from the same source as 291 €2014/ton. Recycling and disposal activities (landfill and incineration) were linked to EXIOBASE based on the physical quantities per year, as shown in the table below. In EXIOBASE there is no specific data set for disposal of wax materials, therefore this was approximated as disposal of plastics.

Table 2. Management of waste packaging materials in the two scenarios, in kg/year.

Packaging material	BAU	Campaign
Waste collection, €2011	242	87
Waste sorting, €2011	186	66
Recycling, plastics, kg	600	207
Recycling, paper, kg	74	31
Incineration, plastics, kg	671	232
Incineration, paper, kg	378	160
Land filling, plastics, kg	352	121
Land filling, paper, kg	198	84

Washing of reusable containers

It was assumed that reusable containers are washed after every use, as they become in contact with meat, fish, etc. According to IDAE (2012), 53% of Spanish households use dishwashers, while the remaining 47% use hand washing. This scenario is considered representative for Zamudio as well. The following activities were included in the LCI:

- For dishwashing, we included the production of the dishwasher, its operation (consumption of water, energy and detergent) treatment of the wastewater generated, as well as the disposal of the dishwasher at the end of its useful life.
- For hand washing, we included water consumption, detergent consumption, energy for water heating, production and disposal of a water heater, and treatment of the wastewater generated.

The dishwasher considered has a capacity of 14 place settings and weights 50 kg (Worten 2019) and has a useful life of 15 years (Binstock et al. 2013). The material composition considered for the end-of-life stage is 86% steel, 3% copper and 11% other materials (Ardente and Talens 2015), the latter taken as plastics. We assumed steel and copper are recycled, while plastics are land filled. During operation, the dishwasher consumes, on a per load basis, 1.05 kWh electricity and 12.47 L water and is used in average 128 times per year (Ibáñez et al. 2009). Dishwashing tablets were assumed to weight 20 g (Amazon 2019). The volume of wastewater was assumed equal to the volume of water used.

In order to allocate these activities to the washing of 1 reusable container, the allocation key chosen was the area of dishwasher tray used. On the one hand, the containers distributed in Zamudio have a size of 33x17.5 cm, equalling 0.058 m². On the other hand, the dishwasher considered has two square trays measuring approximately 0.5x0.5 m each. Thus, the dishwasher has a capacity of 0.5 m² per load and washing one container uses 11.6% of this capacity.

Based on a survey in Spain (Ibáñez et al. 2009), water use during hand washing is increased by a factor 8 compared to a dishwasher. Due to lack of data, detergent use was considered to be equal to dishwashing (20 g detergent to wash 14 place settings). Concerning energy use, we made an estimate of the amount of thermal energy required, expressed in MJ, assuming water is heated from 15 °C to 35 °C in a water heater with an efficiency of 82% (Smarter House 2019). The resulting energy requirement is 0.1 MJ/L water used. The source of energy to provide this heat was taken from IDAE (2012) as 21.5% electricity, 40% natural gas, 0.1% coal, 25.9% liquefied petroleum gas, 10.1% diesel and 1.7% renewable, the latter modelled as biomass.

The life cycle of the water heater was included, considering a device weighting 12 kg (Progasca 2017) with an assumed useful life of 15 years. During this useful life, the water heater is considered to deliver 1,516 GJ in hot water, resulting from an annual energy use in Spanish households of 0.852 tons of oil equivalent, of which 19% is associated to water heating (IDAE 2012). With these data, it can be calculated that 1 MJ for water heating consumes 12 kg/1,516,000 MJ = 7.92E-06 kg of equipment, i.e. water heater per MJ delivered. The end-of-life stage was modelled assuming the

material characterization of the water heater is the same as for the dishwasher, and so is the fate of the embedded materials.

Washing of reusable bags

It was assumed that bitsybags are washed 2 times per year in a washing machine. We included the production, use and disposal of the washing machine. The main data source for this process was an LCA study on washing machines (Yuan et al. 2016). From this study we obtained the weight (75 kg) and material composition (44% steel, 43% plastics, 2% glass, 8% aluminium, 3% copper) of a washing machine, as well as its life span (10 years), use frequency (133 uses/year) typical load (60% of a maximum load of 6 kg), water use (88.3 m³ in 10 years), electricity consumption (517 kWh in 10 years), detergent consumption (20 kg in 10 years) and wastewater production (equal to the volume of water used). At the end-of-life stage, we included the disposal of the washing machine materials, considering metals are sent for recycling while the remaining materials are land filled.

Based on the number of bitsybags distributed in Zamudio according to BCN Ecology (1840 units weighting 10 g each), washing machines are estimated to wash annually 36.8 kg of bitsybags.

Educational activities

The waste prevention campaign in Zamudio involved educational and awareness-raising activities, carried out by dedicated personnel. The estimated cost per year was 750 €2019 according to BCN Ecology.

Rebound effect

The rebound effect was included in the study by performing two steps. First, the life cycle costs of the BAU vs. Campaign scenario were obtained by simulating the two scenarios in the LCA software SimaPro, where a difference of 560 €2019 was obtained, implying a higher cost for the Campaign scenario. In a second step, a saving of 560 €2019 was added to the Campaign scenario, considering the average expenditure in Spain according to its final demand of goods and services in EXIOBASE.

13.3.6 Social footprint Overall results

Table 3 below shows a summary of the total scores obtained, for the two scenarios, as well as the reduction induced by the Campaign scenario compared to BAU. The table shows the results with and without the rebound effect. When the rebound effect is excluded, it can be seen that life cycle costs are 5% higher for the campaign scenario. This cost increase is responsible for the rebound effect, which is taken into account in the lower half of the table, where the life cycle costs are equal for both scenarios.

Table 3. Results for life cycle cost, productivity impact, income redistribution, and social footprint for the two scenarios, excluding or including rebound effect.

Indicator	BAU	Campaign	Campaign reduction (%)
Results excluding rebound effect			
Life cycle cost (€2019)	11,860	12,420	-5%
Productivity impact (€2019, PPP, u.w.) (A)	157,711	140,086	11%
Income redistribution (€2019, PPP, u.w.) (B)	8,182	7,340	10%
Social footprint (€2019, PPP, u.w.) (A-B)	149,529	132,746	11%
Results including rebound effect			
Life cycle cost (€2019)	11,860	11,860	0%
Productivity impact (€2019, PPP, u.w.) (A)	157,711	135,177	14%
Income redistribution (€2019, PPP, u.w.) (B)	8,182	7,080	13%
Social footprint (€2019, PPP, u.w.) (A-B)	149,529	128,097	14%

It can be seen in the table that the BAU scenario leads to a higher detrimental effect than the Campaign scenario in the PI, but also a higher beneficial effect through the IR. However, when the two indicators are combined in the SF, the net effect is a lower footprint for the Campaign scenario, with a reduction of 11% when the rebound effect is excluded, and 14% if this effect is included.

13.3.7 Contribution analysis

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. shows the results for the social footprint for the two assessed scenarios, displaying the contribution from different involved activities in the supply chain, as well as the rebound effect due to the difference in cost between the two scenarios. The figure shows both positive and negative values. The former is interpreted as a footprint with socially detrimental effects, while the latter are interpreted as the opposite, that is, a socially beneficial effect. The total footprint is the combination of these two effects.

Figure 1. Contribution analysis for the social footprint.

The results show that most of the footprint (81% of the total value) in the BAU scenario is associated to the supply chain of plastic packaging, followed by that of packaging paper (16% of the total value). The remaining activities, namely the disposal of all this packaging as waste shows a minor contribution to the footprint, especially when we consider the beneficial effects from recycling, which are shown in the figure with a negative sign.

In the Campaign scenario, the contribution analysis shows that the contribution of packaging material production is smaller (40% of the total value) and dominated by plastic materials. In this scenario, most of the social footprint is associated to the supply chain of washing (dishwashing plus hand washing) the reusable containers, which represents 61% of the total footprint. It can be seen that most of this is associated to dishwashing rather than hand washing. The social footprint of dishwashing is mainly contributed by the supply chain of the dishwasher manufacturing rather than its use phase. Also, the graph shows the rebound effect associated the increased life cycle cost induced by the Campaign. This cost increase was modelled as average spending for goods and services in Spain, and leads to a beneficial effect (a social footprint of negative sign), although with an overall low magnitude compared to the remaining activities in this scenario.

13.3.8 Difference analysis

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. graphically shows the difference between the two scenarios, breaking the system down into the same activities considered in the contribution analysis performed in the previous section. The values are calculated as the score for the Campaign scenario minus the score for the BAU scenario. When this subtraction leads to a negative value (shown in green in the figure), this is interpreted as the Campaign scenario leading to a beneficial effect, and vice versa.

Figure 2. Difference between the social footprint of the Campaign and BAU scenarios. Positive values (in red) constitute a higher footprint for the Campaign scenario, while negative values (in green) constitute a lower footprint for the Campaign scenario.

This figure shows where the Campaign scenario involves an improvement with regard to BAU. Clearly, most of this benefit is found in the avoidance of plastic production processes. This can be also seen in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, which breaks down the difference analysis at the level of individual activities in EXIOBASE. In that table, it can be seen that the Campaign scenario leads to a reduction in the externalities associated to plastics production in developing countries such as China or in Africa. Besides plastics production, the Campaign scenario also shows benefits associated to the lower packaging paper demand, as well as in several waste management activities, although with an overall small relative relevance. On the other hand, the campaign scenario leads to an increased social footprint regarding several activities, such as the supply chain of reusable container washing, as well as in plastics recycling. The latter is due to the lower amount of plastics available for recycling in the Campaign scenario. This means increased quantities of raw materials for primary plastic production need to be produced, typically in developing countries.

Table 4. Difference analysis for the social footprint at the level of activities in EXIOBASE. Negative values are interpreted as the Campaign scenario leading to a benefit when compared to the BAU scenario. The table shows only those individual processes contributing at least 3% of the total social footprint.

EXIOBASE activity	Unit	Difference Campaign - BAU
Total of all processes	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-21,432
Remaining processes	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-12,048
Plastics, basic {CN_TW} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-5,362
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products {WF} (linked)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-4,759
Copper production {CN_TW} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-4,574
Chemicals nec {CN_TW} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-2,606
Chemicals nec {IN} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-2,551
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products {WM} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-2,349
Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys and first products thereof {ES} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-2,299
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products {WE} (linked)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,953
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products {CN_TW} (linked)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,768
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products {CN_TW} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,559
Paper {ES} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,458
Plastics, basic {WA} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,367
Plastics, basic {DE} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,314
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products {IN} (linked)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,230
Chemicals nec {WM} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,074
Chemicals nec {WF} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-1,008
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products {WA} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-980
Chemicals nec {WA} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	-877
Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c. {CN_TW} (linked)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,006
Re-processing of secondary copper into new copper {CN_TW} (linked)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,035
Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys and first products thereof {WA} Terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,037
Production of electricity by hydro {ES} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,261
Chemicals nec {IN} (linked)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,270
Cultivation of crops nec {WF} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,283
Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment {WA} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,333
Waste water treatment, other {WF} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,585
Extraction of crude petroleum and services related to crude oil extraction, excluding surveying {WA} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,787
Production of electricity by solar photovoltaic {ES} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	1,954
Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment {ES} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	3,140
Production of electricity by wind {ES} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	3,875
Plastics, basic {ES} (terminated incl cap)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	3,991
Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c. {WA} (linked)	€2019, PPP, u.w.	5,146

Geographic notation in EXIOBASE: CN_TW: China including Taiwan; WF: Rest of the World – Africa; IN: India; WM: Rest of the World – America; WE: Rest of the World – Europe; ES: Spain; DE: Germany; WA: Rest of the World – Asia.

13.3.9 Conclusions

The main findings of the social footprint study can be summarized as follows:

- The results of the waste prevention campaign, when extrapolated to the entire population of Zamudio, lead to a lower social footprint than the current situation. The value of externalities in the Campaign scenario is 11% lower, however due to the rebound effect associated to the slightly higher life cycle cost of the Campaign, the net social benefit increases to 14% compared to the current situation.
- It must be highlighted that the rebound effect is subject to uncertainty, as it is assumed that reduced disposable income resulting as a consequence of this campaign will be spent according to average spending in Spain. This might not reflect reality accurately.
- In the Campaign scenario, a substantial part of the social footprint is associated to the supply chain of washing (dishwashing plus hand washing) the reusable containers, which represents 61% of the total footprint. It can be seen that most of this is associated to dishwashing rather than hand washing. The social footprint of dishwashing is mainly contributed by the supply chain of dishwasher components manufacturing.
- Most of the social footprint benefit associated to the Campaign is found in the avoidance of plastic production supply chains, often taking place in developing countries such as China or in Africa. Besides plastics production, the Campaign scenario also shows relevant benefits associated to the lower packaging paper demand, as well as in several waste management activities, although with an overall small relative relevance.
- In addition to the data collected, and the valuations obtained in the study, users experience a change in their routines since at home, for those who buy meat or fish once a week, home storage becomes simpler because the same container can be stored in the refrigerator without having to pass through the food or generate contaminated wrappers of remains and / or juices that usually smell bad. Is even more convenient because although it must be planned at the time of purchase to be able to go to the trade with the packaging, odours that those waste generate at home disappear, and the use of the containers in the sidewalk decreases noticeably.

13.3.10 References

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13.4 Documental updating

1.7.1. Online workshops with pilots' leaders

Following the calendar of the Social Actions, regular online workshops will be held between PILOTS leaders and BCN as T4.1 coordinator. A kind reminder will be sent to the involved partners before the foreseen date taking into account the current forecast and future changes in the calendar.

1.7.2. Social Action Plan updating

Every 6 months an updated version will be uploaded and sent to the partners to be reviewed and approved.

14 Interaction with Communication & Dissemination

Plan and Business Model

The Social Action Plan includes all the innovative environmental education activities and strategies to the local target groups described in Chapter 4 in order to increase awareness and knowledge, build new skills and values, promote active participation and, finally, to generate behavioural and habits changes towards sustainable development.

To spread and communicate these local actions in order to get the maximum participation and effectiveness, some general tools and strategies (as they are defined in the Communication and Dissemination Plan) will be used. On the other hand, the Social Action Plan will generate news and also tools that must be used in the Local and General Communication Plan.

A similar interaction will come about the Development of the Business Models, where it would be needed to explain the results of the social actions implemented during the project in the frame of the different business opportunities detected.

So, since WP4 (innovative social actions), WP6 (eco innovative solutions) and WP7 (communication and dissemination) are strongly related, it is important to create synergies among them, in order to avoid overlapping and, specially, to be sure that we take advantage of all the opportunities generated.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan provides guidelines to lead pilots in their local communication. Taking these into account, each Social Action developed in the framework of the project must be considered as a potential new both for local targets involved in the action and for the general interested targets (other municipalities, researchers, companies, NGO's, etc.). In this sense, a strong relationship between pilot leaders, WP4 leaders and WP7 leaders is needed, as it is described in the Communication & Dissemination Plan (D7.1).

Also, for those responsible for WP6 is necessary to take into account the communication tools and results of the different actions, to promote all the eco innovation solutions and social actions developed during the project in the framework of the different business models defined.

The following scheme tries to exemplify these links and synergies between WP4, WP6 and WP7:

Fig. 16 *Interaction among WP4, WP6, WP7 and WP9*

As an example, a protocol to avoid overlapping have been developed with Aclima. The responsible for communication of each partner must complete the Annex 1 'Contents delivery' of D7.1 Communication Plan, every time they carry out an action to be considered newsworthy. The information in this Annex 1 could be used to create a new sheet of 'Qualitative Reporting' about Pilot's Social Actions within WP4 by the coordinator of the Social Action Programme, BCN, with the available information.

Thus, it is important to make it clear in Annex 1 if it is whether a new of dissemination or a Social Action (there is a section at the end of the annex 1 where it can be chosen). If the social Action option is marked, Aclima will send the annex 1 to BCN and BCN will decide if a new sheet is created and sent to the pilot to be completed or an existing sheet will be updated.

15 Annexes

15.1 Calendar

Fig. 17 Social Actions forecast

15.2 Common indicators

Each pilot has to report the impact of the implementation of each Eco solution.

Some indicators calculated are common in all Pilots, others are specific to each one. The KPI's can be found in the data-model attached to each implementation and the can be checked here:

<https://social-actions.waste4think.eu/>

Initially, an excel sheet for each Pilot (Zamudio, Halandri, Seveso and Cascais) was created for quantitative monitoring. That excel has been merged with the qualitative reporting template in the on line Data Model, as explained before.

15.3 Baseline survey proposal

In order to develop the needed SURVEY to calculate the BASELINE (scenario BEFORE any action of the waste4think is developed) for the indicators related to the SOCIAL ACTIONS you should include the following Basic Questions in this initial survey.

Take note that it is a proposal and it should be adapted to the local conditions. Nevertheless, please send to BCN the questionnaire starting to apply:

1. Do you develop any activity of "waste prevention"?

If the answer is "YES", add the following question:

1a. Which type of waste prevention activity do you usually do?

The pollster should insist to obtain as much as examples of activities as possible. Sometimes respondents try to simplify.

This list of examples is only for the pollster to take note of the answers of the respondent. The respondent SHOULD NOT see the options.

	List of prevention activities	Selection of the options
1	Use of reusable shopping bags/shopping trolley/shopping basket	
2	Home composting	
3	Drink tap water (with or without filter jug)	
4	Buy products with refundable packaging	
5	Buy bulk products	
6	Donation or exchange not used products	
7	Buy second hand products	
8	Fix furniture or electrical appliances	
9	Fix clothes or shoes	
10	Measures to reduce food wastage	
11	Rent do-it-yourself tools or other products	
12	Others:	

If the answer is "NO", add the following question:

1b. But do you know any type of waste prevention activity?

If the answer is "YES", add the following question:

1b1. Which type of waste prevention activity do you know?

The pollster should insist to obtain as much as examples of activity as possible. Sometimes respondents try to be simplified.

This list of examples is only for the pollster to take note of the answers of the respondent.

	List of prevention activities	Selection of the options
1	Use of reusable shopping bags/shopping trolley/shopping basket	
2	Home composting	
3	Drink tap water (with or without filter jug)	
4	Buy products with refundable packaging	
5	Buy bulk products	
6	Donation or exchange not used products	
7	Buy second hand products	
8	Fix furniture or electrical appliances	
9	Fix clothes or shoes	
10	Measures to reduce food wastage	
11	Rent do-it-yourself tools or other products	
12	Others:	

2. Do you do waste separate collection at home?

If the answer is "YES", add the following questions:

2a1. Which type of fractions do you separate at home? List all of them.

For each type ask:

2a2. How often do you delivery these fractions to the collection system? Select from daily, two-three times a week, once a week, once a month, other frequencies.

The pollster should insist to obtain as much as examples of actions as possible. Sometimes respondents try to simplify.

This list of examples is only for the pollster to take note of the answers of the respondent. NOT SHOW the list.

	List of fractions/Delivery frequencies	Daily	2/3 times a week	Once a week	Once a month	Others frequenc.
1	Bio waste					
1	Foodwaste					
2	Paper-cardboard					
3	Packaging					
3	Plastics					
4	Glass					
5	Bulk goods					
6	Vegetal Fraction					
7	Electrical appliances					
8	Clothes and shoes					
9	Hazardous products					
10	Batteries					
11	Others:					

If the answer is "NO", add the following question:

2b. Why don't you do you separate waste at home? List the main reasons.

This list of examples is only for the pollster to take note of the answers of the respondent.

List of reason	
1	Don't have space at home to do the separation
2	Don't have time to do the separation
3	Don't know how to do the separation properly
4	Don't have the material to do the separation at home (different bins)
5	It is not hygienic and causes smells and other inconveniences at home
6	Don't have selective waste containers near
7	Waste containers are difficult to access or open
8	Do the waste separation is not compulsory
9	I pay my tax, I don't need to do efforts
10	I am angry with the local authority and don't want to collaborate
11	Others:

6 PREVENTION habits, do you have any habit in order to avoid waste generation? yes no DK/NA/REF

6a if yes Can you mention one ? _____

- | | | |
|--|---|---------------------------|
| 1. I purchase products in bulk | 5. I use products in a responsible way | 10. I reduce food wastage |
| 2. I purchase concentrated, family size, or rechargeable items | 6. I avoid single usage products | 11. Home composting |
| 3. I am part of a fair purchase group | 7. I use reusable nappies | 12. Other |
| 3. I visit reuse centres, charity shops etc. | 8. I reduce the consumption of paper | 13. Not relevant answer |
| 4. I drink tap water / public water fountains | 9. I prefer on-line communications and invoicing | 14. DK/NA/REF |

7 In the last 4 years, have you participate in any action, or received information from the Waste4Think project?

- YES
 NO
 DK/NA/REF

7a if yes, Which one do you remember?

Pilot Meeting	Tv spot	School activity	University Activity
Radio news	Public Event	Social Networks	
info. poster	Peper Note	Web page	others _____

PUNTI INFORMATIVI
 INCONTRI PUBBLICI Activity X

7b If not !: its a pity we couldnt reach you with such important information. Please tell us which are the **proper communication channels** we can use to inform you about the local services and policies?

- | | | |
|--|---------------------|-------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Personal e-mail | answer e mail | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> whats app | answer telefon numb | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Call | answer telefon numb | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Peper letter | adress | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> With your utility bill | | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Municipal paper nesletter | | _____ |
| <input type="checkbox"/> DK/NA/REF | | |

8 What's your knowledge (meaning and details) of the Pay As You Throw scheme implemented?

Have No idea	not informed	not very well informed	3	4	Im very well informed	<input type="checkbox"/> DK/NA/REF
1	2	3	4	5		

9 How did your *prevention* habits behave after the introduction of Pay As You Throw?

My habits have decreased	not decreased	not increased	4	5	my habits have increased
1	2	3	4	5	

9a How did your *separation* habits behave after the introduction of Pay As You Throw?

My habits have decreased	not decreased	not increased	4	5	my habits have increased
1	2	3	4	5	

10 A lot of cities in the EU are planning strategies to improve VMS. From your experience: ¿Which policy do you think would be the best one to foster sustainable habits ?

- a Applying fines for those who don't comply
 b Rewarding those that have good habits
 c Charging the service according to each household habit (PAYT)
 d Investing in voluntary campaigns
 f DK/NA/REF
 e Other: _____

11 ¿How do you evaluate your family's behaviour in...

11a WASTE SEPARATION ?

We are not making any effort				We're doing a big effort
1	2	3	4	5

comments: _____

11b WASTE PREVENTION ?

We are not making any effort				We're doing a big effort
1	2	3	4	5

comments: _____

12 Do you have suggestions or issues to point out to improve the Pay As You Throw scheme?

15.5 ANNEX Details of the integration of the W4T ICT tools in the SA

15.5.1 Zamudio

In general terms, during all the actions and activities in Zamudio the games and apps will be explained to the citizens and how to use/play (Z1.1 and Z1.2).

Z1.5, Z4.2 and Z4.3 have been deployed before the tools were available, so it has not been possible to use them.

Social Action code:
Z1.3 Citizens Science
Ecosolutions used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
In the workshop it will be explained to people how the app works so they can use it on their own during a citizen's science activity.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Some smart phones with downloaded applications and a projector to explain how to play.
Calendar
December 2019

Social Action code:
Z1.4 "Non bota zer" campaign
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
They will distribute the dictionaries of "zer bota non" and at the same time it will be informed about the existence of an app to be able to know to what fraction it is necessary to throw everything.
Calendar
February 2019

Social Action code:
Z2.1 Learning materials application
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP1 Prevention and reuse • DP2 Source separation and recycling • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • DP4 Product Life Cycle • DP5 Waste Tax • DP6 Monitoring of waste generation • MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MG2. SUNFLOWER • MG3. TREASURE MACHINE • Ways2Sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Schools will use these learning materials in class.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers
Calendar
January 2019

Social Action code:
Z2.2 Self-composting
Ecosolutions used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • MG2. SUNFLOWER
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Schools will use these learning materials at school to improve the compost process.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers.
Calendar
January 2019

Social Action code:
Z2.3 Light packaging prevention campaign
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP1 Prevention and reuse • DP6 Monitoring of waste generation • MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME • MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION • Ways2Sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Schools will use these learning materials at school to try reducing light packaging.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers
Calendar
February 2019

Social Action code:
Z2.4 Improve separate collection and prevention
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP2 Source separation and recycling

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • DP5 Waste Tax • DP6 Monitoring of waste generation • MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME • MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION • Ways2Sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Schools will use these learning materials at school to try improving separate collection.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Computers
Calendar
February 2019

Social Action code:
Z3.1 General campaign
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Hold a meeting with NGOs and food retailers to explain how the app works and so that it can start to be put into operation.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smart phones.

Social Action code:
Z3.2 Creative cooking course
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App • DP1 Prevention and reuse
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Prepare a meal with donated food and explain to people through which app the food has been obtained and how it works.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smart phones, place to cook and donated food.
Calendar
May 2019

Social Action code:
Z3.3 Food App
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

The best form to understand through creative cooking course and other promotional actions

Social Action code:
Z4.1 Diagnosis

Ecosolution/s used:

- Local Trade App

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

Meeting to see through the app how everything is working and discuss how to improve.

New materials, equipment, etc. needed

Smart phones.

Calendar

June 2019

Social Action code:
Z4.4 Citizen App campaign

Ecosolution/s used:

Citizen App

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

Visits to the merchants to discuss how to get the most out of the app and explain to them how it works.

New materials, equipment, etc. needed

Smart phones.

Calendar

December 2019

Social Action code:
Z5.1 Community composting plant

Ecosolution/s used:

- DP3 Home compost/Food waste
- MG2. SUNFLOWER

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

An on-site visit to the community composting plant with the schools so that the students can see how the composting plant is working after using the learning materials at the school.

New materials, equipment, etc. needed

Computers.

Calendar

January 2019

Social Action code:

Z6.1 General information
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP5 Waste Tax • Virtual City game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Put a tent in the centre of the town for citizens to approach and the street educator can make a demonstration of how the apps work.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphone and tent.
Calendar
March 2019

Social Action code:
Z8.1 Day festivals
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ways2Sort • Virtual City game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Put a tent where the party is held so that citizens can get closer and the street educator can make a demonstration of how the apps work.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphone and tent.
Calendar
May 2019

Social Action code:
Z8.2 Popular meals
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ways2Sort • Ecodesign game • Virtual City game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Put a tent where the party is held so that citizens can get closer and the street educator can make a demonstration of how the apps work.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphone and tent.

Social Action code:
LAN party
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual City game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Put a tent where the party is held so that citizens can get closer and the street educator can make a demonstration of how the apps work.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Smartphone and tent.
Calendar
July 2019

15.5.2 Halandri

Social Action code
H1.1 Vocational School
Ecosolution/s used:
DP1 Prevention and reuse DP2 Source separation and recycling DP3 Home compost/Food waste DP4 Product Life Cycle DP6 Monitoring of waste generation MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME MG2. SUNFLOWER MG3. TREASURE MACHINE MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
<p>The Ecosolutions will be used in the context of the Environmental Program and the Technology Program of the school (non-typical education), with a specific focus on waste management lessons in the 4 specific thematic areas (source separation and recycling, prevention/reuse, Home compost/food waste, monitoring of waste generation) that have been identified since March '17. The games will be used to support core actions based on DP1-6 and also actions which the schools themselves develop based on the guidelines provided by the Waste4Think team. Where available, data from the apps will be analysed to assess the impact of the program to the students.</p>
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Manuals for the apps, possible need for PCs and/or tablets
Calendar
Educational actions in schools begin on mid-October at the earliest (depending on the school).

Social Action code
H1.2 Gymnasium
Ecosolution/s used:
DP1 Prevention and reuse DP2 Source separation and recycling DP3 Home compost/Food waste DP4 Product Life Cycle DP6 Monitoring of waste generation MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME MG2. SUNFLOWER MG3. TREASURE MACHINE MG4. RESOURCE COLLECTION Ways2sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

The Ecosolutions will be used in the context of the Environmental Program of the school (non-typical education), with a specific focus on waste management lessons in the 4 specific thematic areas (source separation and recycling, prevention/reuse, Home compost/food waste, monitoring of waste generation) that have been identified since March '17. The games will be used to support core actions based on DP1-6 and also actions which the schools themselves develop based on the guidelines provided by the Waste4Think team. Where available, data from the apps will be analyzed to assess the impact of the program to the students.

New materials, equipment, etc. needed

Manuals for the apps, possible need for PCs and/or tablets

Calendar

Educational actions in schools begin on mid-October at the earliest (depending on the school).

Social Action code

H2.2 Use of the eco-design game

Ecosolution/s used:

Eco-design game

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

During a series of lectures students will be asked to play the developed eco-design game, following its instructions.

New materials, equipment, etc. needed

Eco-design game

Calendar

Use of eco-design game will take place during the winter semester 2019

Social Action code

H3.3 Feedback to the citizens & H3.4 Extension of the new collection

Ecosolution/s used:

Local Trade App
 Citizens App
 Virtual City Game
 Planning Game

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

The citizen app will find the heaviest use, since it is expected to provide information on the new system, and also collect feedback which can be extremely important in the rolling out phase of the introduction of the brown bin in a whole municipal section. The Local Trade App will provide positive publicity to local enterprises which use effectively the new system and so act as an incentive, especially in the centre of the municipality where heavy commercial activity may be found. The two

games will: 1) raise awareness of the benefits of the new system and so ease the adoption from citizens/players and 2) provide data (scenario created by players) which can be used to optimize the new system.

Calendar

The extension of the new collection system (introduction of the brown bin) started in November 2018 in a section which corresponds to approximately 10% of the population of Halandri. Extension to the rest of the municipality will take place accordingly, based on lessons learned from this initial extension to the general public. All of the apps will be introduced to the target groups as soon as possible.

Social Action code

H4.1 Citizens Science

Ecosolution/s used:

Citizen App
Virtual City Game
Planning Game

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

The primary Ecosolution is the Citizen App. The results of the surveys from the citizen science action will be introduced in the Citizen App to promote good habits adopted by local enterprises. The two games can be used by the Citizen Science group to further advance their knowledge in the inner workings of waste management and thus create a solid core in the society of the municipality with extensive understanding of waste management and its implications.

New materials, equipment, etc. needed

Possibly tablets or computers, printed manual of the apps

Calendar

The citizen science group is already working. The apps will be introduced to the group as soon as they are available.

Social Action code

H4.2 Promotion of best consumption habits

Ecosolution/s used:

Food App
Citizen App
Virtual City Game
Planning Game

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action

The Citizen App will raise awareness of good consumption habits, by indicating and promoting in a positive way good trade practices, thus attempting to create a market for enterprises which adopt

good habits (good trading habits are also mirrored to a great extent to good consumer habits). The two games will raise awareness on the general effect these habits have, both to the waste management system of the municipality and to the city as a whole.

New materials, equipment, etc. needed

Promotional materials for the apps, printed manuals, possibly CDs to be distributed at public places

Calendar

The Ecosolutions should be introduced to their target groups as soon as they become available.

15.5.3 Seveso

Social Action code:
SE 1.1 – dinners with waste
Evolution/s used:
Citizen’s App, Ways2Sort, Ecodesign game, Virtual city game, Planning game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The citizen app and the serious games will be explained to citizens during dinners; the most complex serious games will be addressed to more sensitized people. Citizen app will be useful to show real time individual generation of waste Ways2Sort will be tested in a collective way to see where to throw difficult items and maybe to set up a competition
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The Citizen App must be able to retrieve data about residual waste individual generation, through Wintarif / Fiware
Calendar
A dinner with waste is foreseen for 21 st September 2018. Others, when the SG are ready and after the implementation of the Citizen App / integration with Fiware data.

Social Action code:
SE1.2 Sensitization activity in public spaces
Ecosolution/s used:
Citizen’s App, Ways2Sort, Ecodesign game, Virtual city game, Planning game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
In public spaces with general target (markets, streets, public events) a demo of Ways2Sort and the Citizen App will be presented. For more complex SG, specific laboratories will be organized targeting high school and university students at FLA (Fondazione Lombardia per l’Ambiente).
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The Citizen App must be able to retrieve data about residual waste individual generation, through Wintarif / Fiware
Roll up with QR code and screenshots of Citizen App and Ways2Sort
Cooperation between Innova21 and FLA to manage laboratories on SG.
Calendar
After the implementation of the Citizen App / integration with Fiware data. Mid 2019? Laboratories with FLA: as soon as SG are ready.

Social Action code:
SE1.4 sensitization in schools
Ecosolutions used:
Ways2Sort, ecodesign game, virtual city game, planning game

Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Students in primary schools will be shown how to use Ways2sort. Students in secondary schools will also see other SG (serious games) and will develop small projects and researches on it. A tablet will be used to show them, linked to the class beamer.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Agreement with teachers. Beta / Final version of the Serious Games.
Calendar
As soon as the beta is available.

Social Action code:
SE1.6 sensitization in private courtyards
Ecosolution/s used:
Citizen's App, Ways2Sort
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Ways2Sort will be used in private courtyard events. The citizen app will be explained. Ways2Sort will be used to see how people behave after responding to a questionnaire on separation of difficult items.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The Citizen App must be able to retrieve data about residual waste individual generation, through Wintarif / Fiware. Roll up with QR code and screenshots of Citizen App and Ways2Sort
Calendar
After the implementation of the Citizen App / integration with Fiware data. Mid 2019? Just Ways2Sort: public events to be organized in spring/summer 2019

Social Action code:
SE2.2 – Virtuous Households – training and monitoring period and S2.4 – virtuous households second stage (focus on waste prevention)
Ecosolution/s used:
Ways2Sort, ecodesign game, Citizen App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The second round of the VH action (foreseen in spring 2019) will be focusing on waste prevention. 10 families will be monitored to check their waste reduction, and the 2 ecosolutions (W2S and ecodesign) will contribute to their training.
Citizen App may be used to invite people to go to local shops where they can use reusable containers etc.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The Ecodesign game should be effective enough to foster good waste prevention habits. Citizen App should be translated in Italian
Calendar
Spring 2019

Social Action code:
SE3.2 – Celebration of ecoevents
Ecoslution/s used:
Ways2Sort, ecodesign game, Virtual City Game, Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
In a specific ecoevent in summer 2019 (maybe AMALO event), a “serious game” session could be organized, maybe in the afternoon before the dinner, to explain the games and sensitize participants, mostly students.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Final version of the SG.
Calendar
June 2019

Social Action code:
SE 4.1 – PAYT monitoring – tax calculation
Ecoslution/s used:
Citizen’s App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The citizen app will be used by citizens to see real time individual generation of waste
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The Citizen App must be able to retrieve data about residual waste individual generation, through Wintarif / Fiware

Social Action code:
SE 4.4 – PAYT - littering monitoring
Ecoslution/s used:
App “Puliamo il Mondo” prepared by ARS and used by Legambiente. Plogging monitoring tool
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Local activists of Legambiente used the app by ARS to monitor the spots where waste is abandoned and littering occurs. The local Marathon Running Club will be involved to monitor constantly a specific path in the city / park to count how many abandoned waste bags are present and for plugging activities (running collecting waste), using specific tools which integrates WhatsApp and google doc. <i>Unfortunately, these actions have been organized only a few times because the app had a lack of flexibility to manage the information.</i>
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The plugging tool will be developed by ARS to integrate WhatsApp messages with a database to store info about bags and pictures.

Calendar

Starting December 2018

15.5.4 Cascais

Social Action code:
C1.1 Preparation Activities
Ecosolution/s used:
No ecosolution used
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The preparation activities comprise actions in designing posters, leaflets and inquiries at technical level to better understand the process of engaging citizens.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Flyers, organic waste bags, key holders.
Calendar
April 2018

Social Action code:
C1.2 Implementation campaign-condominium meetings
Ecosolution/s used:
DP2 Source separation and recycling
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Meetings with condominiums will be made according to the planned agenda of each building management as we will add the Waste4Think project in their agenda. However, it is noteworthy that the condominium agenda proposal did not work well in the first stages of the participant registration as the participation rate in these meetings is very low and it only occurs every six months.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Flyers, organic waste bags, key holders.

Social Action code:
C1.3 Gammification - award system
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP5 Waste Tax • Ecodesign game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
Despite having our own app (Citypoints Cascais) additional tax knowledge is of added value for project management as we can further the knowledge of younger family members and school students.
Ecodesign game will help to achieve these goals in a more engaging method (nontax related).
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Learning materials related to the tools and games

Social Action code:
C1.4 Promotion of W4T Apps and games

Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App • Citizen App • Citizens App • Ways2Sort • Ecodesign game • Virtual City game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
All games and apps are designed for different ages and target audience. But we believe that these tools can be used simultaneously by different groups of people in both domestic and school context as it will give a family discussion about the subject. It might even help the discussion within different target audiences on management context (EMAC Team and citizens).
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Only the applications

Social Action code:
C1.5 Feedback
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens App • DP6 Monitoring of waste generation
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
We hope that both the citizens app and DP6 monitoring will help to share the message about the waste production evolution in the pilot area during the duration of the project as we will share the waste rate and production in our activities.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The application itself and the related information from the monitoring process.

Social Action code:
C2.1 Information to Landlords
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens App • DP3 Home compost/Food waste
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
In rented houses, for both tourism short renting and normal renting, we will talk to landlords to promote their awareness on the project, the project's goals and values. For this, we think the applications and food waste are the best items to engage with the people renting the houses as they are easy to use and complete by home users. It will also benefit a cleaner environment in their houses and neighbourhood which, we believe, might add value to their house rental offer.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The applications, organic waste bags and compost information.

Social Action code:
C2.2 Dedicated campaign
Ecosolution/s used:
Citizens App
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
For tourist engagement, we seek to give a simple, quick solution to adopt during their short stay to reduce waste production and promote separation. We believe both apps will help with the awareness of these users.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The applications, organic waste bags and compost information.

Social Action code:
C3.1 Learning materials use
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • MG1 IMPROVEMENT GAME • MG2. SUNFLOWER
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
The learning materials will be, mostly, used as support for our existing activities from our school activity program within the waste and environment segment. We intend to reach all schools in the surrounding area.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
The applications, organic waste bags

Social Action code:
C3.2 Serious games
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ways2Sort • Ecodesign game • Virtual City Game • Planning Game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
We intend to use the serious games as relevant awareness tools in direct contacts with participants, in schools and other collective awareness activities. These Serious Games are extremely useful to continuously contact citizens as they can be promoted via internet, school awareness actions and other activities in the pilot area. They add tremendous value to our social activities.
As some of these tools are pointed towards adults or general citizens, we intend to reach them by introducing these tools in schools, some older aged students might become familiar with the tools and use it in family context.
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Tool use information (manuals)

Social Action code:
C3.3 EMAC own activities
Ecosolution/s used:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food App • Citizens App • DP3 Home compost/Food waste • DP5 Waste Tax • Ecodesign game
Description of the integration of the Ecosolution in the Social Action
<p>The apps will be used in school context as additional value to our own activities. We will test their application and start a discussion about waste management in older student classes.</p> <p>The learning materials will also be an addition to some of our activities, as they will enrich the offer of our program. Hence, they will be used outside the pilot area and waste4think project, reaching far more students and communities.</p> <p>The ecodesign game will be used within the context of the NOVA SBE university as they have numerous sustainability related activities and students' groups where this will surely be appreciated.</p>
New materials, equipment, etc. needed
Tool use information (manuals)

15.6 ANNEX analysis of Zamudio surveys

15.6.1 1. First Result: Baseline

The study population used in the following analysis is that corresponding to the total number of inhabited dwellings within the municipality of Zamudio, corresponding to 1,259 dwellings. But the survey is applied to 334 dwellings, I feel these are considered as "the sample".

- a) The first table indicates the percentage of the population that buys within Zamudio and the percentage that buys outside Zamudio. This information is obtained from one year of consumption patterns for meat, fish, and fruits and vegetables.

In this table, which is the basis for locating our area of study, it is observed that most of the population purchases their products within the municipality of Zamudio.

	MEAT	FISH	FRUITS AND VEGETABLES
Usually commerce IN Zamudio	93%	84%	93%
Usually OUT Zamudio	7%	16%	7%

Fig. 18 Excel: QUESTIONNAIRE OF BUYING HABITS (answers) BASELINE

- b) The second table is the result of the purchasing habits of the surveyed population. (*Total surveys 334 dwellings - is considered as the sample)

It is observed that 1 to 2 times a week is where most purchases occur, both meat, fish and fruits and vegetables.

Purchase habits BASELINE	MEAT	FISH	FRUITS&VEGETABLES
3-4 times per week	24%	20%	38%
1-2 times per week	67%	70%	58%
Every 2 weeks	7%	7%	4%
Once per month	2%	2%	1%

Fig. 19 QUESTIONNAIRE OF BUYING HABITS (replies) BASELINE

From the above table, which is in percentage, we are interested in obtaining the number of times purchases for this is estimated one year (52 weeks) as a reference.

The times are calculated by taking an average of purchases per week and projecting it to a year.

- For purchases made 3-4 times a week, an average of 3.5 is taken.
- For purchases made 1-2 times a week, an average of 1.5 is taken.
- For purchases made every two weeks, the 52 weeks are divided into 2 weeks.
- For purchases made once a month the 12 months are taken.

As an example, to determine the times that the population buys meat 3 to 4 times a week, the following formula is used to calculate the times of annual purchase:

$$(24\%) \text{times of purchases} \times (1,259) \text{dwellings} \times (3.5) \text{average purchases} \\ \times (52) \text{ weeks of the year} = (55,925) \text{ number of times of purchase}$$

Obtaining the result of the number of times the inhabitants of Zamudio buy meat, fish and fruits and vegetables during a year. This result is higher for fruits and vegetables and lower for fish.

Purchase habits	MEAT	FISH	FRUITS & VEGETABLES
3-4 times per week	55.925	46.747	86.142
1-2 times per week	65.579	68.643	56.485
Every 2 weeks	2.330	2.409	1.231
Once per month	256	354	170
TOTAL VECES	124.090	118.152	144.028

Fig. 20 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1

- c) The third table is to determine the percentage of the Zamudio population that used the reusable bag before the implementation of the W4T, the percentage of the population that made their purchases online and the percentage of the population that did not carry anything at the time of making their purchases.

In the initial survey, the following options were added so that the population could indicate what they were carrying at the time of purchase: (1) trolley, (2) reusable bags, (3) tupperware, (4) backpack, (5) nothing or (6) home shopping.

Of these options the only ones that replace the plastic carrier bag are "the cart, the reusable bags and the backpack", therefore to determine the percentage of people who use reusable bags these data were used as a basis and to determine the percentage of people who use reusable packaging the data from "tupperware" were used.

Purchase habits	MEAT				FISH				FRUITS&VEGETABLES			
	Reusable carrier	Reusable wrap	Online	Nothing	Reusable carrier	Reusable wrap	Online	Nothing	Reusable carrier	Reusable wrap	Online	Nothing
Usually	30%	0%	1%	9%	28%	0%	0%	10%	30%	1%	0%	9%
Sometimes	6%	1%	0%	5%	6%	0%	1%	5%	6%	0%	1%	4%
Never	64%	99%	99%	86%	66%	100%	99%	85%	64%	99%	99%	87%
TOTAL	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

			%				%				%	
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Fig. 21 Excel: QUESTIONNAIRE OF BUYING HABITS (answers) BASELINE

** It is assumed that the respondent falls in the attempt to please the interviewer, presenting an inconsistency in this table and is that people specify that for their purchases generally do not take anything to load it back, but when asked about when they carry nothing, they say they never carry anything, therefore the data will be considered only the reusable bag.*

With the information from the tables above, it is possible to determine the weight of the plastic carrier bags in which the inhabitants of Zamudio take their purchases home. These bags are delivered / sold by traders to people who do not carry reusable bags to carry their purchases back.

In order to carry out the calculation, the frequency factors were valued as follows:

- Usually (25%)
- Sometimes (50%)
- Never (100%)

The maximum value corresponds to never since those who never carry reusable bags to make their purchases are those who are generating this waste of single use and those who usually carry reusable bags do not generate the waste of the plastic carrier bag.

The weights are calculated using the following data: the percentage of people who carry their reusable bags when they go shopping, the number of times the Zamudio population makes their purchases of meat, fish and fruits and vegetables, and finally the weight of each unit of plastic carrier bag.

As an example, to determine the weight of plastic carrier bags for people who, when buying meat, never carry a reusable bag and make this purchase 3 to 4 times a week. The formula is used:

$$(100\%) \text{ valuation of never} \times (54,993) \text{ times meat is purchased 3.5 times per week} \\ \times (64\%) \text{ times they do not carry a reusable bag} \times (1.81\text{g}) \text{ weight of a plastic bag}$$

Obtaining the result of the total weight of the plastic, translated into carrier bags, for one year's purchases at Zamudio. This total weight was 521 kilos, before the implementation of the waste4think project.

Purchase habits	MEAT			FISH			FRUITS&VEGETABLES			Peso en gramos
	Usually	Sometimes	Never	Usually	Sometimes	Never	Usually	Sometimes	Never	
Carrier										
3-4 times per week	7.576,7	3.232,7	64.452,4	5.974,4	2.406,6	54.719,4	11.592,6	4.668,2	100.210,3	254.833,4
1-2 times per week	8.884,6	3.790,8	75.578,1	8.772,7	3.533,9	80.349,2	7.601,5	3.061,0	65.709,3	257.280,9
Every 2 weeks	315,7	134,7	2.685,5	307,8	124,0	2.819,3	165,6	66,7	1.431,6	8.050,9
Once per month	34,7	14,8	295,1	45,2	18,2	414,0	22,9	9,2	198,2	1.052,4
TOTAL	16.811	7.173	143.011	15.100	6.082	138.301	19.382	7.805	167.549	521.217

Fig. 22 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1

- d) The fourth table is to determine in which wrappers they sell meat, fish or fruits and vegetables to the inhabitants of Zamudio, wrappers that will later go inside the carrier bag.

	EPS+film	plastified paper	wax paper	ultra light plastic bags	carrier plastic bag	composta bles bag	reusable container	reusable bag	other
MEAT	10%	38%	11%	5%	35%	0%	0%	0%	0%
FISH	9%	16%	34%	5%	36%	1%	0%	0%	0%
F & V	2%	5%	3%	46%	40%	3%	0%	1%	0%

Fig. 23 Excel: CUESTIONARIO DE LOS HÁBITOS DE COMPRA (respuestas) BASELINE

With the information from the tables above, plus some market data, it is possible to determine the annual weight of the wrappers in which traders wrap meat, fish, and fruits and vegetables at the time of sale.

In order to determine these total weights, we first obtained the weights per unit and in grams from each package separately, which are detailed in the following table:

Envoltorios	Dimensiones	Pesos (gr)	Proveedor
EPS+film	210 x 155 x 25 mm	7,2	Plastipapel
Plastified paper	38 x 27 cm	6,45	Globalcarnica
Wax paper	26 x 36 cm	1,99	Tukistore
Ultralight plastic bags	17 x 1,4 x 11,5 cm	0,99	Bolsas de plástico
Carrier plastic bag	25,6 x 1,8 x 21,5 cm	1,81	Todoalmacen
Compost-table bag	30 x 20 x 60 cm	0,027	Plaxi
reusable container	-	-	-
reusable bag	16,5 x 14,5 x 2,5 cm	141	Luxja
other	-	-	-

Fig. 24 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 4

In addition to these weights it was essential to know extra market data, in relation to the quantities consumed of meat, fish and fruits and vegetables, which in the first instance will serve us to determine the rations consumed individually.

- Per capita consumption in kilos per person per year, for meat and fish, obtained from the Report on Food Consumption in Spain 2017, Government of Spain - Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food.
- Recommended weekly fruit and vegetable intake frequencies (counting these as a unit and not by weight), obtained from Recommended Rations, Complutense University of Madrid - Department of Nutrition - Faculty of Pharmacy.
- Weight of each ration in grams of meat and fish, obtained from recommended Rations, Complutense University of Madrid - Department of Nutrition - Faculty of Pharmacy.

*From now on the categories of meat and fish will be analysed in a different way to the category of fruits and vegetables, this is because the objective is to determine the real weight of the wrappers, when buying meat and fish these generally wrap them in the same wrapper, unlike the fruits and vegetables that according to variety will have a different wrapper.

So for the fruits and vegetables the portions will be established by unit and not by gram, unlike meats and fish.

The data obtained are the following: per capita consumption and quantity per serving of meat and fish, and weekly portions of fruits and vegetables. These are detailed in the following table.

	MEAT	FISH	FRUITS&VEG
Annual per capita consumption (kilograms)	47,6	23,7	171,2
Annual consumption per capita (grams)	47.600	23.730	171.240
Weekly rations	3,5	3,5	35
Quantity per serving (gr)	135	138	113

Fig. 25 Table of consumption per capita and rations.

Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1

In order to be able to work with these data, we first determined the average number of people per dwelling in Zamudio; we considered the data for the year 2018. Using the following formula:

$$\frac{(3.236) \text{ Zamudio inhabitants}}{(1.259) \text{ Zamudio dwellings}} = (2,57) \text{ persons per dwelling}$$

Second, for fruits and vegetables, the number of "packages" per person per week was determined. Using the hypothesis that each wrapper fits 5 units.

$$\frac{(35) \text{ weekly rations}}{(5) \text{ units per wrapper}} = (7) \text{ personal f\&v wrappers}$$

Taking these factors and along with the market data we were able to obtain the annual number of rations per capita for meat and fish and finally the annual package of purchases at Zamudio. Using the following formulas, as an example for the meat category:

$$\frac{(47.600 \text{ g}) \text{ annual per capita consumption}}{(135 \text{ g}) \text{ quantity per ration}} = (352,6) \text{ number of rations}$$

$$(1259) \text{ total dwellings} \times \frac{(352,6) \text{ number of rations}}{(2,35) \text{ persons per dwelling}} = (172.709) \text{ packages comprados in Zamudio}$$

The category of fruits and vegetables will be worked using the following formula: the category of fruits and vegetables will be worked using the following formula:

$$(7) \text{ personal packaging} \times (52) \text{ year} \times (1.259) \text{ dwellings} = (458.276) \text{ packages comprados in Zamudio}$$

Thus obtaining the number of portions per capita for meat and fish and also the quantities of packages in unit and annual where they wrap meat, fish and fruits and vegetables.

	MEAT	FISH	FRUITS&VEG
Number of rations per capita	352,6	172	-
Annual Zamudio package	17.2709,5	84.229	458.276

Fig. 26 Table of rations and annual package. Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1

Finally and with the previous data we can determine the total weight of the wrappers of the different categories. Using the following formula as an example for meat wrapped in EPS+film:

$$(172.709,5) \text{ paquete Zam anual} \times (10\%) \text{ venta env} \times (7,2 \text{ g}) \text{ peso env} \\ = (128.727,5) \text{ peso total de env anual}$$

Obtaining this way that the total weight of the wrappers in which the inhabitants of Zamudio make the purchase of meats, fish and fruits and vegetables during a year being this one of 1.752 kilos.

	EPS+film	plastified paper	wax paper	ultralight plastic bags	carrier plastic bag	compos-table bag	reusable container	reusable bag	othr	TOTAL	
MEAT	128.727,5	419.759,1	39.136,8	7.788	110.673,5	9,7	0	0	0	706.094,6	
FISH	52.911,6	85.076,9	56.996,8	4.104	54.228,8	25,4	0	0	0	253.343,7	
FR&VEG.	69.758,7	149.981,2	30.848,9	207.183,4	334.948,4	340,1	0	204,9	0	793.265,6	
										TOTAL (gr)	1.752.703,8

Fig. 27 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 1

15.6.2 First Result: Kit

The following data correspond to the result of the survey carried out once Zamudio users obtained their kit, composed of two tupperware, one for meat and one for fish, four reusable bags for fruits and vegetables and also a Boc'n'Roll.

From the above data it is assumed that the results of purchases made inside or outside Zamudio are maintained and consumption habits do not change, therefore this information is maintained and helps us to develop information referring to users with kit.

The following table shows the consumption habits reflected in the number of times Zamudio residents buy meat, fish or fruit and vegetables.

Purchase habits	MEAT	FISH	FRUITS & VEGETABLES
3-4 times per week	55.925	46.747	86.142
1-2 times per week	65.579	68.643	56.485
Every 2 weeks	2.330	2.409	1.231
Once per month	256	354	170
TOTAL VECES	124.090	118.152	144.028

Fig. 28 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2

a. The first table is to determine the percentage of Zamudio's population using the reusable bag once the W4T project was implemented, the percentage of the population that made their purchases online and the percentage of the population that did not carry anything at the time of making their purchases.

In the survey applied, the following options were added so that the population could indicate what they were carrying when they made their purchase: (1) trolley, (2) reusable bags, (3) tupperware, (4) carrycot, (5) backpack, (6) nothing or (7) home shopping.

It was established that the reusable bag and the Tupper will be considered only as replacement data, as these were delivered in the kit.

Purchase habits BASELINE	MEAT				FISH				FRUITS&VEGETABLES			
	Reusable carrier	Reusable container	Online	Nothing	Reusable carrier	Reusable container	Online	Nothing	Reusable carrier	Reusable container	Online	Nothing
Usually	84%	55%	0%	5%	63%	47%	0%	8%	89%	5%	5%	5%
Sometimes	5%	24%	0%	21%	11%	26%	5%	26%	5%	5%	5%	13%
Never	11%	21%	0%	74%	26%	26%	95%	66%	5%	89%	89%	82%
TOTAL	100%	100%	0%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Fig. 29 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2

With the information from the tables above, it is possible to determine the weight of the plastic carrier bags in which Zamudio residents take their purchases home. These bags are delivered / sold by traders to people who do not carry reusable bags to carry their purchases back.

In order to carry out the calculation, the frequency factors were valued as follows:

- Usually (25%)
- Sometimes (50%)
- Never (100%)

The maximum value corresponds to never since those who never carry reusable bags to make their purchases are those who are generating this waste of single use and those who usually carry reusable bags do not generate the waste of the plastic carrier bag.

The weights are calculated using the following data: the percentage of people who carry their reusable bags when they go shopping, the number of times the Zamudio population makes their purchases of meat, fish and fruits and vegetables, and finally the weight of each unit of plastic carrier bag.

As an example, to determine the weight of plastic carrier bags for people who, when buying meat, never carry a reusable bag and make this purchase 3 to 4 times a week. The following formula is used:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (100\%) \text{ valuation of the never} \times (55,952) \text{ times meat is bought 3.5 times a week} \\
 & \times (11\%) \text{ times they do not carry a reusable bag} \\
 & \times (1.81 \text{ g}) \text{ weight of a plastic bag} \\
 & = (10,655.2 \text{ g}) \text{ real weight of plastic meat bought 3.5 times a week}
 \end{aligned}$$

The result is the total weight of the plastic, translated into carrier bags, for one year's purchases at Zamudio. This total weight was 257 kilos, after implementing the Waste4Think project.

Purchase habits	MEAT			FISH			FRUITS&VEGETABLES			Peso en gramos
	Usually	Sometimes	Never	Usually	Sometimes	Never	Usually	Sometimes	Never	
3-4 times per week	21.310,4	2.663,8	10.655,2	13.359,9	4.453,3	22.266,4	34.876,2	4.103,1	8.206,2	121.894,5
1-2 times per week	24.989,0	3.123,6	12.494,5	19.617,4	6.539,1	32.695,7	22.868,8	2.690,5	5.380,9	130.399,6
Every 2 weeks	887,9	111,0	444,0	688,3	229,4	1.147,2	498,2	58,6	117,2	4.182,0
Once per month	97,6	12,2	48,8	101,1	33,7	168,5	69,0	8,1	16,2	555,1
TOTAL	47.285,0	5.910,6	23.642,5	33.766,7	11.255,6	56.277,8	58.312,3	6.860,3	13.720,5	257.031,2

Fig. 30 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2

b. The second table is to determine in which wrappers they sell the meat, fish or fruits and vegetables to the inhabitants of Zamudio, wrappers that will later go inside the carrier bag. These values are kept constant from the baseline.

	EPS+film	plastified paper	wax paper	Ultra light plastic bags	carrier plastic bag	compostables bag	other
MEAT	10%	38%	11%	5%	35%	0%	0%
FISH	9%	16%	34%	5%	36%	1%	0%
F&V	2%	5%	3%	46%	40%	3%	0%

Fig. 31 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2

With the information from the tables above, plus some market data, it is possible to determine the annual weight of the wrappers in which traders wrap meat, fish, and fruits and vegetables at the time of sale.

The estimation of these total weights of wrappers is made using the same methodology as the Baseline, detailed in point 1, using the data of the individual weights of the wrappers. In addition to

these weights it was essential to know extra market data, in relation to the quantities consumed of meat, fish and fruits and vegetables, which in the first instance will help us to determine the rations consumed individually.

In this case the annual package data in Zamudio is calculated differently, since the project is implemented and we will count in addition to the data from the reusable container. Using the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} & (7) \text{ personal wrappers} \times (52) \text{ year} \times (1,259) \text{ dwellings} \\ & \times " (5\%) \text{ times carrying reusable container} " \\ & = (24,120) \text{ packages purchased at Zamudio} \end{aligned}$$

Thus obtaining the number of portions per capita for meat and fish and also the quantities of packages in unit and annual where they wrap meat, fish and fruits and vegetables.

	MEAT	FISH	FRUITS&VEG
Number of rations per capita	352,6	172	-
Annual zamudio package	95.445	39.898	24.120

Fig. 32 Table of rations and annual package. Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2

Finally and with the previous data we can determine the total weight of the wrappers of the different categories. Using the following formula as an example for meat wrapped in EPS+film:

$$\begin{aligned} & (172,709.5) \text{ zamudio annual package} \times (10\%) \text{ sale env} \times (7.2\text{g}) \text{ packaging weight} \\ & = \text{total annual packaging weight} \end{aligned}$$

Obtaining this way that the total weight of the wrappers in which the inhabitants of Zamudio make the purchase of meats, fish and fruits and vegetables during a year being this one of 551 kilos, after the implementation of the project.

	EPS+film	plastified paper	wax paper	ultralight plastic bags	carrier plastic bag	compos-table bag	Other	TOTAL
MEAT	71.138,9	231.972,1	21.628,2	4.303,9	61.161,7	5,3	0,0	390.210,2
FISH	25.063,4	40.299,6	26.998,5	1.944,0	25.687,3	12,0	0,0	120.004,9
FRUITS&VEG.	3.671,5	7.893,7	1.623,6	10.904,4	17.628,9	17,9	0,0	41.740,0
						TOTAL		551.955,1

Fig. 33 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 2

15.6.3 Comparative Results: Baseline and Waste4Think:

The data used in the calculation of the reduction in weight of carrier bags and packaging are those derived from the previous analysis, taking into account the data provided in the survey carried out before the implementation of the project and contrasting them with the survey carried out once the project has been implemented.

For carrier bags, 51% of the waste was reduced and for packaging, 69% of the waste was reduced.

REDUCTION WITH IMPLEMENTATION (kg/year)	Baseline	Waste4Think	REDUCCIÓN	% REDUCCIÓN
Carrier bags	521,2	257,03	264,17	51%
Packaging	1.752,70	552	1.200,70	69%

Fig. 34 Excel: Baseline Results Analysis - Waste4Think, sheet 3

15.6.4 Recycling habits

Recycling habits of the Zamudio surveyed population.

MEAT					
	Goes to the specific container the same day	Throws the same day commingled	Uses the specific container when he takes the rest of the waste.	Throws with the rest of the waste commingled	Reuse
Usually	47%	0%	26%	3%	13%
From time to time	26%	13%	18%	11%	18%
Never	26%	87%	55%	87%	68%

FISH					
	Goes to the specific container the same day	Throws the same day commingled	Uses the specific container when he takes the rest of the waste.	Throws with the rest of the waste commingled	Reuse
Usually	71%	3%	13%	3%	5%
From time to time	16%	8%	26%	8%	5%
Never	13%	89%	61%	89%	89%

FRUITS & VEGETABLES					
	Goes to the specific container the same day	Throws the same day commingled	Uses the specific container when he takes the rest of the waste.	Throws with the rest of the waste commingled	Reuse
Usually	13%	0%	26%	3%	34%
From time to time	18%	8%	16%	13%	26%
Never	68%	92%	58%	84%	39%